

Not Just Extra Chairs in the Classroom: International Student Struggles with Loneliness and Isolation

by

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Dedication Page

I would like to dedicate this research to the three strongest women I know: my mother, my wife, and my daughter.

Abstract

Keywords: international students, isolation, loneliness, mixer events, social networking

International students in a Japanese university struggled with issues of loneliness, lack of belonging, and feelings of not mattering. These issues inhibited their ability to form friendships with domestic students. This study sought to investigate causes and find actionable solutions to international student social networking issues. Participants and data collected in Cycle 1 consisted of international students who offered their experiential insights through ten semi-structured interviews. Alongside domestic and international students, steps were designed, implemented, and evaluated in Cycle 2 in order to empower the international student minority group, and encourage interaction and social bonds between international and domestic students. The Cultural Awareness Circle was founded and met on Mondays throughout the course of the 2023/24 fall semester. 12 meetings were held in which both international and domestic students planned and implemented two mixer events with the goal of increasing international and domestic student interaction and fostering a sense of community. Evaluating the results of the Action Research study included a thorough assessment through member checking, questionnaires, and an exit interview with a participating international student. Student participants and collaborators/allies provided feedback that assisted in the research design and evaluation process. The study concluded that the Cultural Awareness Circle empowered student participants to plan and implement two mixer events that positively impacted international students' ability to form friendships and interact with their fellow classmates. Implications for the organization included increased intercultural interaction, integration of international student populations, and increased feelings of positivity towards the university by both international and domestic students.

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Section One: Introduction

The title of this dissertation comes from an excerpt from an international student (IS) during Cycle 1 interviews. This student, describing IS experiences at this university stated, “They [IS] have no purpose of being there. Like just for the attendance. They're an extra chair” (Amil, Cycle 1 Interview, 2022). The purpose of this Action Research was to understand the struggles and neglect faced by IS at a science university in Japan. Intervention sought to improve conditions for these members of the university’s international community. The research will hopefully provide a blueprint on methods to decrease loneliness and isolation among IS in Japanese universities.

The report begins with an introduction to the research related to international student struggles to provide context and background to the study. This introduction includes an overview of the problem of practice that the research addresses, the research purpose, research questions, description of the research context and participants, as well as a brief synopsis of the research design.

The Results section of the report outlines the outcomes of the intervention. In this section, the ways in which the participants describe and interpret their experience of the issue are described. The Literature Review provides descriptions and critiques of existing perspectives from the literature on the topic. The Contextualization section analyzes the context of the research through the lens of the institution and extant literature. The implications of the research study will be described including specific examples of how findings were used in the practice setting and suggestions for areas of future investigations.

Problem Statement

The problem of practice I observed was that my university of employment has a minority percentage of IS (3%) (see Table 1) who experience social isolation, lack of belonging, and loneliness. Loneliness and isolation are defined as follows, “Social isolation is categorized by whether an individual belongs to a social network; loneliness, however, refers to the perception that one's intimate and social

needs are not being met” (Girmay & Singh, 2019, p. 2). Belongingness, by contrast, involves solid support networks and a sense of connection with the university (Glass & Westmont, 2014). Loneliness can be viewed as the absence of a sense of belongingness. Yanguas et al. (2018) clarifies loneliness as the “lack of a social network, the absence of a circle of people that allows an individual to develop a sense of belonging, of company, of being part of a community” (p. 302).

Table 1

International student demographics (slightly redacted)

International Students												Student Nationalities											
719												17											
Country	Undergraduate School		Master's		Doctoral		Specialist		Research Student		Total												
	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women													
China	261	150	62	29	7	3	2	1	12	5	532												
South Korea	108	30	3	-	2	1	-	-	-	-	144												
Malaysia	9	1	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	12												
Indonesia	3	3	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7												
Vietnam	1	1	2	2	1	-	-	-	-	-	7												
Taiwan	1	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	4												
Total	385	186	70	34	17	6	2	1	13	5	719												

1/2

Country	Undergraduate School		Master's		Doctoral		Specialist		Research Student		Total
	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	
Egypt	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	2
Thailand	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
India	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1
Sri Lanka	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1
Bangladesh	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Jordan	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1
Nigeria	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1
France	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1
America	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Canada	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Australia	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Total	385	186	70	34	17	6	2	1	13	5	719

(As of May 2021)

During Cycle 1, I discovered that IS have trouble interacting and forming friendships with domestic students (DS). Essentially, IS have difficulty developing social networks, particularly with DS,

and expressed sentiments of loneliness and isolation during interviews. IS at this institution reported that it was difficult to make friends due to linguistic and cultural differences. One IS even described making friends with DS as “almost impossible” (Salim, Cycle 1 Interview, 2022). This isolation and loneliness made some students feel neglected by the academic community, with one student even saying they sought mental health treatment at the campus health center and took medicine for depression (Sira, Exit Interview, 2023). While some campus “international” events were held in previous years, participants revealed that these events were not well-attended by DS, and therefore did not help IS interact with their fellow Japanese counterparts. According to participants, these international events did not help IS integrate into the academic community.

Assimilation troubles may be the result of an absence of cultural clubs and/or cultural centers to adequately accommodate global English-speaking students. At first, I presupposed that English as a Medium of Instruction (EMI) might serve to better accommodate international learners’ needs. Dearden (2014) clarifies the meaning of EMI as involving the use of the English language to conduct courses in a country where the first language of the people (L1) is not English. The results of Cycle 1 suggested that the absence of English language programs was not a big issue faced by many IS at this academic institution, and the assumption that IS need more English was perhaps the result of my own researcher biases. Essentially, as an American, I would benefit from increased access to English programs. The data that emerged through Cycle 1 interviews suggested that many of the students were already studying in English, with many reporting that all their classes were taught in English. Contrary to my expectations, Cycle 1 data suggested a deeper psychological issue than was initially anticipated. Most (90%) of the IS reported feeling lonely and having difficulty making friends and social networks; particularly with regard to forming friendships with DS. Considering that Japanese students form a large bulk of the student community (97%), IS reported often feeling isolated or having only superficial friendships with fellow students in their classes.

Research suggests many issues may arise when IS feel social isolation. These issues include negative feelings of being the victim of xenophobia (Girmay & Singh, 2019), feelings that domestic students were insincere in their attempts to make friends with IS (Girmay & Singh, 2019), negative impressions of IS by teachers and faculty members (Girmay & Singh, 2019), and lack of engagement in student support services (Wawera & McCamley, 2020). Additionally, Yanguas et al (2018) tell us that social loneliness can have very consequential psychological repercussions. The authors (2018) found that social loneliness led to psychological issues such as anxiety, depression, psychological stress, and higher overall morbidity rates. Social loneliness is also a predictor of suicidal ideation and suicidal behavior (McClelland et al., 2020).

Intervention efforts that increase integration and interaction between IS and DS may be an all-around win for university stakeholders. For the country, it may lead to higher student retention and graduation rates, contributing to a stronger knowledge economy by promoting brain gain/circulation (Kruanak & Ruangkanjanases, 2014). Essentially, the country would benefit from attracting more international academics. The university may also benefit by increasing appeal to future IS. Better accommodating IS may increase the outside attractiveness of the institution thus, in turn, increasing the number of IS enrollment. Increasing IS may also improve the university's global rankings (McAleer et al., 2019). DS stakeholders may also win by strengthening their cultural and linguistic fluency through cross-cultural interaction (Galloway et al., 2017; Phuong & Nguyen, 2019). Increased cultural and linguistic fluency prepares DS for multicultural experiences in the modern global workforce (Briguglio, 2014). Finally, IS may benefit by increasing a sense of belonging within the academic community by potentially achieving better grades resulting in higher retention rates (Bowman et al., 2019; Bronkema & Bowman, 2019; Krieg et al., 2024; Rasco et al, 2023).

Purpose of Research

The purpose of this Action Research is to understand the struggles of IS at a private university in an urban area and develop interventions that lead to an increased sense of belongingness and positive feelings about the university. Knowledge generated from this research is expected to inform this higher education institute, and possibly other higher-education institutions, how to better accommodate their international student population.

Research Questions

Cycle 1 Questions

- 1.) What are the experiences and perceptions of IS at a private university in Japan?
- 2.) How do IS navigate the current system?
- 3.) How effectively do IS form social friendships and networks with DS?

Cycle 2 Questions

- 1.) What is the impact of an intentional IS support program on the belongingness experienced by IS students at a private university in Japan?
- 2.) How effectively do IS form social friendships and networks with DS?
- 3.) How can IS and DS social networks and friendships be improved?

Overarching Question

- 1.) How can interventions be developed and implemented to increase a sense of belongingness and positive feelings among IS at a private university in Japan?

The answers to these research questions guided and informed me regarding IS perceptions about institutional accommodations and feelings of belonging within the academic community. As my goal was to build a better atmosphere of acceptance for IS, the Action Research in this paper sought to replace feelings of isolation and loneliness, with improved integration and increased feelings of

belonging to the academic community. It was my hope that better integration would lead to more positive feelings about the university and its academic community.

The research conducted in this dissertation took place at a science university in Tokyo. Most of the research was conducted in a room in the main lecture hall. This room is referred to as the International Lounge (IL) (see Figure 1). This room was equipped with an Apple TV, DVD player, sofas and beanbags, and shelves with English comic books, tea and coffee, and other amenities. Due to the relaxed nature of this room, I felt it could provide IS and DS with a comfortable safe space to convene and discuss student issues. Stringer and Aragón (2020) discuss the importance of understanding the physical and symbolic space within an institution where a research project will be undertaken. The authors (2020) stress the importance of these spaces to the occupiers and highlight how problems may arise from interrupting the status quo, comforts, or expectations. For this reason, among others, the IL was chosen as a space to conduct research in order to give participants a comfortable space separate from classrooms where specific roles and expectations are firmly established. Essentially, if students take on a victim role in the classroom, I wanted to create a new environment free of negative associations.

Figure 1

Students utilizing International Lounge

Participants/Collaborators/Stakeholders

The main participants in my research were IS and DS. These members were recruited through convenience sampling (Parker et al., 2019). These members frequented the International Lounge (IL) space and volunteered their time to help the ongoing research efforts. As the International Lounge provided a good mix of international and domestic students who were presumably interested in international matters, it seemed the ideal location for the participants to meet. Both domestic and international students participated in the action research with the goal of improving conditions for IS at the university. IS participated in 11 interviews, ten during Cycle 1, and one exit interview conducted at the end of Cycle 2. This “exit interview” was conducted with a participating IS after the intervention. Both DS and IS participated in strategizing better ways to integrate IS in this academic institution. Ultimately, both DS and IS planned and attended mixer events aimed at building transnational friendships and networks.

Staff members of the *Kyoyo*, or liberal arts department, and administrators in Building 1 acted as allies in creating positive change at the institution. Accessing the IL, reserving the room for events, acquiring money for food and drinks, and having events officially advertised through the school website required these stakeholders’ involvement. Additionally, they proved essential participants in the events, with several members joining and helping. One of the participating members was the department head, who helped validate the event among institution members. It was also important to keep internal stakeholders in the loop regarding the intervention process. This helped spread the word of the events among teachers, staff members, and students.

On a final note, I would be remiss not to include my teachers and classmates at Northeastern University as invaluable stakeholders in my research plan. Their guidance, support, and experience-based advice steered the project in the right direction. I frequently met with my chair, Northeastern professors, and classmates to inquire about the most suitable Action Research approaches.

Positionality

When discussing positionality within Japanese society, it was important to consider that I am a *gaikokujin*, or an “outside country person.” Although I have lived in Japan for 17 years and have a permanent residency, I will perhaps perpetually be viewed as an outsider. As a person perceived as an outsider, there was a risk of Japanese staff members viewing my work as tinkering with the Japanese system or Japanese way of doing things. It was also important to understand that *senpai/kohai* (senior/junior) relationships in Japan may cause students to feel compelled to cooperate with any professor’s requests. This pressure to cooperate may be compounded by the requirement for respectful behavior towards older people.

I also remained aware that, as a teacher, students may sense I have power over their academic achievement in this institution, even when I am not directly filling a role as their teacher. I sought, whenever possible, to alleviate these concerns and assure students that participation was strictly voluntary. It was also important to make the student aware that participation would not positively nor negatively affect their grades or status within the institution.

Additionally, it was important to consider my position as a member of the liberal arts department in a science university. My assumption, and perhaps biases, lead me to believe that language professors are not given the same consideration as science and engineering professors at science institutions. During one department meeting I attended, for example, it was mentioned that language teachers should refrain from giving students too much homework as it interferes with their lab work. Another important consideration was my professor rank within the department. As an assistant professor, I am presumably not given the same clout and respect as an associate or professor-ranked teacher.

Finally, members of my department are assigned *tantou*, or task leader positions. It was vital to understand and work with other *tantou* members in a manner that did not undermine their

responsibilities. The IL, where much of my research took place, is led by my senior colleague. I avoided, whenever possible, usurping this professor's position as tantou, and thus made sure to consult them on all matters involving the IL. For a visual representation of my positionality, please see Figure 2.

Figure 2

Four Layers of Positionality Diagram

Synopsis of the Research Design

The action research presented in this paper followed a Grounded Theory framework (Glaser & Strauss, 2017). Noble & Mitchell (2016) explain that Grounded theory (GT), is an approach to research where theory generation is data-driven, or grounded in the data, allowing the researcher to collect and analyze data simultaneously.

During Cycle 1, I employed 10 semi-structured interviews with IS at my institution. Interviews were transcribed and coded using Open, Axial, and Selective coding techniques (Scott & Medaugh, 2017; Vollstedt & Rezat, 2019; Williams & Moser, 2019). Member checking was also employed to triangulate the data derived during the interview and coding process. The data from these interviews led me to believe that IS may feel they do not belong or matter, and experience loneliness. To evaluate this before

Cycle 2 intervention, I sent out a belongingness questionnaire to 300 IS on my campus. 111 IS responded and the data supported my belief that IS felt isolated.

In order to combat the issue of loneliness and not mattering/belonging, I decided to form a Cultural Awareness Circle during Cycle 2 where IS and DS could form a community to interact, discuss issues of cultural awareness, and strategize ways to better integrate IS into the academic community. This circle included me, and students gathered by convenience and snowball sampling (Parker et al., 2019). This group met on Monday afternoons to discuss cultural differences, strategize ways to improve conditions for IS, and plan school events such as IS and DS mixers. The goal of the circle's work was better assimilation and integration of IS within the academic community.

I, along with members of the Cultural Awareness Circle, planned and hosted 2 mixer events in the International Lounge space in the Lecture Hall on campus. These events were attended by both IS and DS. After each event, a questionnaire was distributed online to both IS and DS who had participated in the events. The goal of these questionnaires was to gauge the efficacy of the events in helping both IS and DS network and build friendships cross-culturally.

Finally, based on the results of the questionnaires, an exit interview was conducted with one IS who had repeatedly indicated in both questionnaires that they had not made friends during the events. Since the number of IS responding negatively in the questionnaires was low, I was particularly interested in this student's experiences. A semi-structured interview was conducted with lasting roughly 30 minutes. This interview was recorded and transcribed. The transcription was coded based on how the data addresses questions posed by the researcher.

Section Two: Results

Cycle 1 Results/Findings

This section will evaluate Cycle 1 findings and how they informed the Cycle 2 action steps. I will review each step taken in response to the identified issues of Cycle 1. I will also evaluate data generated through Cycle 2 questionnaires and interview data to gauge the efficacy of the intervention steps undertaken.

Cycle 1 Description of Data

Cycle 1 focused on the experiences of international students in a Japanese university. Ten semi-structured interviews were conducted with IS on one campus to gain a better glimpse of these students' experiences. This resulted in over four hours of recorded audio. The audio was then transcribed resulting in 91 pages of written transcripts with 770 quotes coded. Initially, these quotes were coded into 24 categories. Using a codebook, these categories were then reduced to 15 threads. These threads were then grouped into the following themes: 1.) Not belonging, 2.) Not mattering, and 3.) Loneliness. I will now discuss the themes and provide quotes from the interviews as evidence of the participants' experiences.

Not Belonging

Belongingness, in the context of a university, involves solid support networks and a sense of connection with the university (Glass & Westmont, 2014). There was evidence of not belonging throughout the ten interviews conducted. These students, as part of a minority group (3% of the student population), felt culturally isolated and revealed they did not encounter other IS in their daily lives. As Fredo (pseudonym) suggested, "there's not that many of us here", indicating that this participant did not encounter many other international students on campus. Interestingly, this student used the term "us" to refer to international people, perhaps due to the researcher also belonging to this perceived group. The pronoun "us", often used to describe IS, appeared 65 times during interviews. The pronoun "them", often used to describe Japanese people, appeared 85 times. This us/them description may be the result

of the societal treatment of international people. Liddicoat (2007), citing Masden (1997), suggests some Japanese hold a “we/they” perspective when describing Japanese vs. non-Japanese people. This may, in turn, affect IS perception of belonging, resulting in an us/them dichotomization.

Belonging is an essential part of college life. Stephens et al. (2015) suggest, that “students’ college success depends on them feeling at home instead of feeling like an outsider” (p. 3). There was evidence in the interview data that IS struggle academically at this institution. Fredo discloses, “I have heard that [...] one foreign student in four actually ends up repeating the year.” This reported high failure rate may theoretically be the result of students not feeling as though they fit in or have a strong support system. Tay (pseudonym) indicated this lack of support systems by stating, “Making friends and finding support systems inside the university and overall, like getting used to the Japanese life. For that one I need some help.” Tay also described the experience of a fellow international graduate student by saying, “[The student] quit the PhD because of the lack of support.” Tay goes on to say that he himself lacked adequate social and academic support from the university. Regarding this aspect, Tay confided, “I think they could have given a much more support.”

Additionally, Tay suggests that Japanese students do not feel comfortable talking with IS and perhaps prefer to distance themselves from others. Tay states, “Japanese people are reserved in general, um, and they like the individuality a little bit more. And so, they like to give every person the space.” Tay supposes that this distancing may be an issue. He goes on to say, “They kind of like, try to keep the distance little bit too too far.” This was echoed in Salim’s (pseudonym) statement, “You have other students in the lab that you try to be close to them but just keep their distance.” This distancing affected international students’ sense of connection with their fellow classmates and lab mates.

Not Mattering

Prilleltensky (2020) defines mattering as “a culture where all of us feel valued and have an opportunity to add value” (p. 25). Feeling as though we matter is essential for psychological health.

Prihadi et al. (2020) suggest that feeling as though students do not matter can lead to low self-esteem, depression, and suicidal ideation. Throughout the interviews, there was a sense that IS felt they did not matter at this institution. As Amil (pseudonym) revealed, "They [IS] have no purpose of being there. Like just for the attendance. They're an extra chair. 'Yes, I am there.' Like, I'm attending, yeah that's it. Like, 'don't fail me.'" This suggestion that IS have "no purpose" does seem to indicate this student did not feel they, or other IS, mattered at this university. Amil also notes, "Many of the other international students, they will just be sitting there as like, they are existing", indicating a lack of purpose for these students in the university environment.

Amil paints a clear picture of not mattering to the academic community by saying, "I feel we are a little bit ignored." Seville's (pseudonym) struggles to fit in perhaps left him with negative feelings towards Japanese people in general. As he stated "Here, people is so weird, and I remember I say 'Good morning' and no one say 'Good morning', or 'How are you?', something like that... and no one respond [...] it's like 'Oh my God, what's wrong with these people?'" Again, the phrase "these people" suggests an us/them dichotomization. This student perhaps views himself as an outsider; something different from the students around him. This lack of reciprocated greeting perhaps made the student feel invisible.

Seville also felt that perhaps people were ignoring him due to something he had done. As he suggests, "Maybe they hate me for some reason. I don't know." He describes people not saying "goodbye" to him as "It's like [the other students] suddenly disappeared." Seville concludes by stating, "For me it's really important to be in a place where I feel comfortable and with that kind of people, that don't say you 'Hi', 'Bye' or even don't talk to you." Seville also suggests that very little effort was made to include him in events. As he explains, "Even there are some events for international students the, I mean the announcement of that event was in Japanese." This suggests that no effort was made to include students who could not speak Japanese, even for events geared for IS. Seville was a student who did not speak Japanese well.

This feeling of not mattering affected students' outward behavior. As Amil stated, "I just had to be there and then like submit uh a report or something, and I submitted in English and that's ah, no exams, or I don't need to listen to what they [lecturers] say." This behavior reflects a belief, on the part of the student, that their level of academic effort and engagement is not important. Essentially, if the student does not feel as though they belong or matter, then perhaps they feel their effort and learning output do not matter as well.

There was also evidence of not mattering in the sense of being neglected. When the student had a problem or concern about their studies or academic life, they were ignored. Blossom (pseudonym) had some trouble in her Japanese class, but when she tried to communicate this with the professor, she said, "He didn't respond." This lack of response may have been an innocent oversight on the part of the teacher, but the student took it as if their problems and concerns did not matter. Cena et al. (2021) warn that even small issues can have a big impact on making IS feel unwelcomed and disrespected.

Loneliness

Girmay & Singh (2019) define loneliness as a condition where one's "intimate and social needs are not being met" (p. 2). Essentially, this has to do with the student's interpersonal relationships with their university peers. This was an issue that was present in nine out of ten of the semi-structured interviews conducted in Cycle 1. This was surprising considering that during the first six interviews, I was unaware of this issue, and my questions were not focused on this matter. Nonetheless, IS reported struggling to form friendships and interpersonal relationships throughout the interviews.

As Fredo said, "There's not that many of us here." This suggests that IS may not have many opportunities to interact with other IS. There was also evidence that IS had trouble interacting with DS. Shin (pseudonym) suggested that making friends with DS may be more challenging. As Shin disclosed, "the thing is, if you want to communicate with Japanese to make Japanese friends, more harder." Salim supported Shin's contention by stating, "I think it's very difficult. It's almost impossible" when asked

how he makes friends with Japanese students. I was surprised by this statement and asked, “Almost impossible?” to confirm. Salim responded to this confirmatory question by saying, “I’m just being sincere.”

Interviewees cited culture and language differences as perhaps being to blame for poor friendship-building with DS. As Blossom stated, “The Japanese students I met in my lab, they are so friendly and try to make connection, but the problem is a language and culture.” I found it interesting that this student cited both linguistic and cultural differences as an issue. Language difficulties may understandably impede friendship formation, but cultural differences cannot be overlooked as an additional hurdle. Robinson et al. (2020) found that international students in a Canadian university sometimes felt intimidated to initiate conversations with host nationals due to reinforced cultural boundaries. Tay (pseudonym) attested to this cultural hindrance by stating, “I think that’s a feeling like even though no matter how much you speak Japanese you’re not a Japanese person, right? So the level of process that you can build with people who are not from the same culture is slightly different.”

There was a sense, from the coded interview data, that the institution and individual staff members were making some effort to alleviate this issue of loneliness among IS. The result of this intervention was either ineffective or awkward for the IS. As Seville (pseudonym) expressed, “At least with the [professor name redacted] professor, I feel like he was, especially in the first week, he was forcing to the students to communicate with me. I mean like ‘Oh you’re going lunch? Say to Seville for going with you.’” This seems to suggest that the professor, while perhaps well-intentioned, may have been creating an ingenuine situation where DS were being pressured to interact with Seville; perhaps reluctantly. This type of interaction seems somewhat involuntary and inorganic. Campus Mate, a university program aimed at helping IS transition to Japanese university life, was also reported to be ineffective at building cross-cultural friendships. As Amil stated regarding Campus Mate, “You don’t make any connections with the

people there. Like you talk to some people and when the time finishes, 'okay, now it's done.'" This suggests there was no lasting effect.

On a positive note, there was some evidence of IS making friends with other IS. Hira (pseudonym) suggested, "Um, actually I don't have so many Japanese friends, so at that time I use in class, like with my international friends like from Chinese, Vietnamese." Additionally, there was a sense that IS could turn to DS for pragmatic problem-solving. Tira (pseudonym), when asked if they had many Japanese friends stated, "Not really. For some of them, like if you really need to talk, if I have like some problems or something like that, I can ask them in the class." This does suggest some interaction and support from DS, albeit not to the point of friendship.

Shi (pseudonym) was the only IS who reported a successful friendship with DS. While having mostly Chinese friends, they reported that their best friend was a DS. Although this student only reported having one Japanese friend, the modifier "best" indicated a deep bond between this IS and DS. It perhaps could be noted that this particular student did not speak English very fluently, and much of our interview was conducted in Japanese. It is possible that her Japanese language skills helped her form this friendship, but other interviewees had reported taking intensive Japanese classes. Presumably, these students were also able to communicate in Japanese.

Conclusion

The Cycle 1 findings suggested IS may feel isolated, and that they do not belong or matter. This is perhaps due to cultural and linguistic differences, paired with a lack of opportunities, and little effort from the university to aid in proper integration. Participants reported having few to no strong friendships or connections with DS outside of classrooms and labs. Programs aimed at assisting IS, felt forced and did not result in lasting bonds or friendships among those interviewed. The findings also suggest that students responded to not belonging or mattering by not engaging in the lectures and giving the bare minimum effort required to pass their courses.

Cycle 2 Action Steps

Cycle 2 intervention sought to address IS belongingness, mattering, and isolation issues. The first intervention was creating a Cultural Awareness Circle comprised of both DS and IS members. The motivation to create this circle was to establish a safe space for IS and DS to interact and discuss issues of cultural differences. It was hoped this would give IS an inclusive environment where these students belong and their voices matter. The Cultural Awareness Circle also strategized ways to bridge the linguistic and cultural gaps and ultimately created mixer events aimed at bringing IS and DS together. Being somewhat cognizant of Japanese interpersonal procedures, I planned this action step around the interpersonal relations concept of *nemawashi* (going around the root). *Nemawashi*, discussed in further detail below, essentially kept other faculty members aware of all action steps planned and assisted in instigating university change without interrupting the Japanese sense of institutional harmony. As many action steps were taken, often overlapping, a timeline of action steps was created for reader clarity (see Figure 3).

Figure 3

Timeline of Cycle 2 action steps

Action Step Goals and Objectives

The goal of the Cycle 2 Action Research was to increase IS assimilation and integration into the academic community, and reduce feelings of loneliness, not mattering, and not belonging among IS. The data from cycle 1 painted a picture of students feeling excluded and neglected or forced into uncomfortable integration situations. Based on these findings, I felt that forming a Cultural Awareness Circle would remedy some feelings of being stranded and alone as a minority group. After discussing the baseline questionnaire conducted at the start of cycle 2, I will talk about action steps taken that were geared toward developing a Cultural Awareness Circle and hosting mixer events to act as a safe space and support system for neglected IS.

Action Step Activities

Baseline Data Gathering

Prior to engaging in the Cycle 2 intervention, a baseline questionnaire (see Appendix D) was sent to 300 international students on the researcher's university campus. The questionnaire was based on Hagerty & Patuský's (1995) Sense of Belonging Instrument (SOBI). The researcher felt drawn to SOBI based on its use of Walker and Avant's (2005) concept analysis model that looks to define a concept based on its defining attributes, case study, consequences and antecedents, and empirical referents. Using SOBI as a framework, the survey was customized to make it more culturally appropriate to Japanese institutions. An example of this customization was distinguishing between making friends in general, and with making friends with DS or IS. I was instructed by the main office to keep the questionnaire to 20 questions. I managed to somewhat adhere to this request by reducing the number of questions to 23.

The goal of this questionnaire was not only to uncover whether international students felt they belonged and mattered, but also to assess issues that may contribute to, or inhibit their ability to form connections and friendships. The questionnaire employed a Likert scale with 1 indicating "strongly

disagree”, and 5 indicating “strongly agree.” The results are discussed in further detail in the Results/Findings section of this dissertation paper.

Nemawashi Strategy - Going Around the Root

Before engaging in any institutional action steps, the researcher felt it was important to acknowledge that staff members are culturally expected to engage in *nemawashi* before bringing up new initiatives in public forums such as meetings. Sagi (2015) suggests that *nemawashi*, a term from gardening that literally translates to “going around the root”, is a method to gain consensus for a project before introducing it in a meeting. A senior colleague of mine offered their perspective and definition of *nemawashi* in a preliminary interview as follows:

Nemawashi means where you talk to people and you get their understanding before you decide anything. You don't talk about it in a meeting. You organize everything before the meeting and the meeting is just a place where you can agree. It's a way to save face. (associate professor and colleague, personal communication, 2023)

Saito (1982) suggests that *nemawashi* sets the proper foundational *kuuki*, or atmosphere, for an initiative. Collaborative decisions are then built on this foundational trust.

Based on the concept of *nemawashi*, the researcher focused on building a grassroots campaign that started with individual conversations in the university hallways, offices, and the proverbial water cooler. These discussions were aimed at building support, allyship, and institutional consensus regarding the need for intervention. These discussions safeguarded against faculty members feeling blindsided by a proposal they were not privy to in a meeting. After gaining institutional support, the Cultural Awareness Circle was founded and began meeting in September of 2023. This group, along with the researcher, planned and hosted events aimed at increasing IS feelings of belongingness, mattering, and integration.

Actions Steps taken by the Cultural Awareness Circle

The Cultural Awareness Circle was a group that met 12 times in the International Lounge of the Lecture Hall building on campus. This group met each week throughout the 2023 fall semester. Roughly 5-10 students met each week on Monday afternoons from 2:40 pm until 4:00 pm. Students were evenly mixed between international and domestic students. Both graduate and undergraduate students took part in the weekly meetings.

The circle typically discussed issues of cultural awareness, cultural differences, IS isolation, and racial discrimination. The goal of the circle was to better integrate IS into the academic community by increasing interaction, networking, and friendship building. Soon after its formation, the Cultural Awareness Circle began strategizing ways to increase interaction between IS and DS. This ultimately led to the implementation of two mixer events hosted by the Cultural Awareness Circle in the International Lounge space.

During meetings, a whiteboard was used to help strategize intervention plans. This whiteboard helped the Circle to remain proactive and focused throughout each meeting, rather than just talking about ideas loosely. Members of the Cultural Awareness Circle, with the assistance of the researcher, developed flyers and questionnaires to both advertise the event and gauge the impact of the events.

Two mixer events were planned and hosted by Cultural Awareness Circle on November 29th, 2023, and December 20th, 2023. The mixer event in November was dubbed “World Snack Event.” The mixer event in December was dubbed “World Holiday Event.” I will discuss each in detail below.

World Snack Event

The World Snack Event started at 1:00 and was slated to finish at 3 p.m. For most of the event, there were 13 students in attendance. There were four Japanese students, and nine international students (all from China and Korea). In addition to 13 students, there were four teachers in attendance. Two teachers were Japanese, and two (including myself) were international. One international teacher

volunteered to lead a game at the end. At first, students were put into three groups with the intention of mixing IS and DS. Groups were changed many times so that everyone had a chance to meet and interact.

During the event and as students were leaving, attendees were asked to scan a QR code to access a questionnaire. Posters with the QR code were displayed on all the doors and tables of the Lounge area. These questionnaires were used to appraise the effectiveness of the event. In addition, follow-up e-mails and member checking were conducted during the days following the event. The results of these questionnaires are discussed later in this paper.

World Holiday Mixer Event

This event was attended by 12 students, roughly half were international. The goal of this event was to have more discussion for the sake of IS and DS integration. Rather than playing games, we focused on increasing interaction time between IS and DS with less teacher focus. In order to accomplish this, students were put into groups with the intent of mixing IS and DS. Groups were changed frequently. The event was two hours long, lasting from 1:00 p.m. to 3:00 p.m.

Similar to the first event, a QR Code to a Google Forms questionnaire was distributed to students. Students could fill out the questionnaire on their smartphones or on a computer. In addition, follow-up e-mails and member checking were conducted during the days following the event. The results of these questionnaires are discussed in the “Cycle 2 Results/Findings” section of this paper.

Participants/Collaborators/ Stakeholders

Several internal stakeholders participated in the action steps throughout the research. The main stakeholders in the research were IS and DS, but teachers in the English Group also participated in the mixer events. Convenience sampling (Parker et al., 2019) was utilized to recruit members who frequented the International Lounge space. Snowball sampling (Parker et al., 2019) was also utilized as initial members recommended friends and acquaintances they felt could contribute. The International

Lounge was chosen for initial convenience sampling as it provides a good mix of international and domestic students who are, presumably, interested in international matters.

Participating students served as members of the Cultural Awareness Circle, meeting weekly and discussing strategies to better integrate IS into the academic community. This circle, or club, discussed matters of cultural awareness, and sensitivity. They also planned mixer events with the purpose of building transnational friendships and student networks. In addition, some of these participating members also helped design questionnaires and translate documents into various languages.

Staff members of the Kyoto liberal arts department and administrators in Building 1 also served as valuable allies in creating positive change at the institution. These members helped advertise the Cultural Awareness Circle, and the events held by the circle. These members also attended events and participated in the activities. In addition, some of these members put poster advertisements on their doors to help promote the circle and its events.

There were several external stakeholders that contributed to this research project. These included parents, university volunteers, and Northeastern professors. These external stakeholders contributed in small ways such as donating snacks for our World Snack event or helping to allocate funds to stock the lounge with food and drinks. Northeastern University professors also contributed to the research project through continued guidance, support, and experience-based advice that helped steer the project in a direction of success. The chair of my doctoral research, Dr. Neil Trotta, also assisted by meeting with me in person as well as corresponding with me through Zoom, telephone, and e-mails. Without his assistance, this project would not have been possible.

Cycle 2 Evaluation

This research followed a qualitative Action Research approach (see Appendix A). Several steps were taken throughout Cycle 2 to measure the effectiveness of the Action Research intervention. These steps included 1.) a baseline measurement at the start of Cycle 2 in the form of 111 collected

Belongingness questionnaires sent to international students at the researcher's campus of employment, 2.) Two surveys distributed during and after IS and DS mixer events, 3.) Frequent Member Checking, and 4.) An exit interview given to an IS member who participated in the Cultural Awareness Circle and mixer events.

Baseline Questionnaire

The baseline questionnaire (see Appendix D) was adapted from Hagerty and Patusky's (1995) Sense of Belongingness Instrument (SOBI). I felt this Likert-style questionnaire was useful for assessing belongingness but needed some customization to better fit the conditions of international student experiences in Japan. Examples of customization include question 11, which reads, "Being international (non-Japanese) is difficult here", adapted from the original question "I feel like an outsider in most situations." The questions needed to be applicable to international students in Japan. The questionnaire was sent to students through the international affairs office and was administered both in English and Japanese. This baseline measurement was essential to gauge 1.) the degree to which the Problem of Practice impacted students prior to Cycle 2, and 2.) the impact of our intervention efforts.

Event Questionnaires

World Snack Event Survey

In addition to the baseline questionnaires, two questionnaires (see Appendix F) were given throughout Cycle 2. These questionnaires were administered after each international/domestic student mixer event. The questionnaires were administered online through Google Forms. Students were given a QR code to take the survey at a time of their convenience after the event.

The first survey and QR code were distributed online on November 29th during the World Snack Event in the International Lounge on campus. The 12-Item Likert-scale questionnaire was developed together with an ally and Cultural Awareness Circle member. This member taught me how to use Google

Forms, and assisted in developing questions to help gauge IS and DS interaction and integration during the event.

World Holiday Mixer Event Survey

This survey was administered after the World Holiday Event on December 20, 2023. The only two changes made to this survey were that answering every question was no longer mandatory and the questionnaire item that stated, “I felt at home and accepted at this event” was changed to “I felt welcomed and accepted at this event.” This change in wording was based on feedback given during member checking, discussed in more detail in the Member Checking section which follows. The first questionnaire, designed alongside a Cultural Awareness Circle member and ally, made answering all questions mandatory for submission. In the interest of maintaining anonymity, particularly with respect to e-mail, I decided to make answering questions optional for the second event questionnaire. The QR code for this survey was on posters in the room and students were asked to scan the code on their way out of the event.

Member Checking

After both the World Snack mixer event and the World Holiday mixer event, I contacted students who included their e-mail in the questionnaire answers. Students’ e-mails were copy-and-pasted into the “bcc” box of the e-mail to preserve anonymity. The e-mail was sent in order to better understand responses to the event questionnaire. In the first questionnaire, for example, I noticed that a few students selected 2 (disagree) to questions such as “I made friends at this event”, and “I felt at home and accepted at this event.” I wanted to get a better picture as to what students were experiencing and how events could be improved in the future.

Exit Interview

As a final measure of the impact of intervention, I conducted a semi-structured interview with a domestic student from China. I prepared an Interview protocol and questions sheet to guide the interview.

This student was chosen based on their answers to the event questionnaire, in which they indicated they had not made friends or felt at home. A large majority of the participants had indicated they had interacted and made friends at the events. This one student repeatedly indicated no positive effect. They also included their e-mail in the questionnaire even when it was not required. I became interested in this student's experiences and wanted to better understand how these events could be improved in the future. When I e-mailed the student, they responded in a way that indicated they were amenable to being interviewed. We set up an interview time and place and agreed to meet. Initially, we agreed to meet at the campus café, but the café was full of students on this day. In order to have a more private and anonymous interview, we both agreed to conduct the interview in the second-floor library.

Cycle 2 Results/Findings

Cycle 2 sought to address issues uncovered during Cycle 1. Initiatives taken in Cycle 2 were designed to address the issues of IS not belonging, not mattering, and loneliness. This study revealed that these issues could indeed be addressed and alleviated through the implementation of an international club or circle and the hosting of multiple mixer events.

Baseline Questionnaire Results

300 copies of the baseline questionnaire were distributed to IS at the researcher's campus of employment prior to intervention. This questionnaire was given to better understand what intervention strategy would be most appropriate in Cycle 2. The students were given two copies of the questionnaires, one in English and one in Japanese. The majority of the questionnaires, 83 of the 111 (74.7%) were filled out in Japanese. This perhaps suggests that a majority of IS felt more comfortable using Japanese than English. The results were color-coded in a spreadsheet in order to account for differences in ethnicity and gender. Of the 300 questionnaires distributed, 111 were returned. There was a response rate of 37%. A large majority of responders were from Asia (76%). 1% were of mixed race, and the remaining 23% did not specify their race. Data from this questionnaire shed light on the

first and second research questions regarding institutional accommodations and IS social friendships and networking.

The results of the questionnaire were then analyzed looking at mean scores across the 111 respondents. A table was created linking the question with the corresponding mean score (see Appendix E). The results of this questionnaire will be summarized with respect to IS belonging, mattering, and sense of isolation. This baseline data-gathering step was important to appraise whether the intervention had an effect on IS. This questionnaire was also implemented to assess whether the difficulties expressed by IS during Cycle 1 could be generalized to the greater IS community at this university.

International Student Belonging

Baseline data suggests that many IS at this university felt as though they did not belong. In response to the questionnaire item “This university feels like home to me”, IS responded with a mean score of 2.88. This low score may indicate that students do not feel they belong as one typically does as a member of a family or home life. Further, students answered the questionnaire item “I feel part of a group at this university” with a mean score of 3.41, indicating room for improvement towards a goal of general agreement. 25 students, or 22.5%, disagreed or strongly disagreed with this questionnaire item, indicating that this was a problem for many IS.

Additionally, there was a sense that the university was not doing enough to integrate these students. Responses to the question “This university does a good job of making international students feel included” were somewhat neutral ($m=3.36$), again indicating room for improvement. There was also a sense that students may struggle to fit in. When asked to respond to “I fit in with other Japanese students at this university”, the mean score was 3.29. A large number of students responded with a 1 or 2 to this questionnaire item (22.5%). This may indicate that many IS feel as though they do not belong with their fellow host national classmates.

There was a positive to take away from this baseline questionnaire. Although Stephens et al.

(2015) suggested that students' college success depends on them feeling at home, there was an indication that IS at this institution planned to persevere. The only questionnaire item that had general agreement was the item "I will definitely finish my degree." This questionnaire item had a mean score of 4.34. Although this mean score is encouraging, it may speak more to IS personal academic dedication than the result of a healthy student environment.

International Student Mattering

Regarding mattering, there was evidence that students do not feel they matter at this institution. In response to questionnaire item "I am an important part of this university", the mean score was 2.91. In fact, 35 students (31.5%) selected 1 or 2 indicating disagreement or strong disagreement. This suggests that nearly one in three students do not feel they are important members of this institution. This feeling of not mattering, along with not belonging, may impact IS positivity, perhaps reflected in the neutral score ($m=3.18$) to the item "I always enjoy being on campus." In other words, if students felt they were important members of the academic community, perhaps they would have more enjoyable experiences on campus.

International Student Loneliness

IS loneliness and friendships with host nationals were perhaps the biggest problems elucidated by the questionnaire data. IS indicated that they did not have many good Japanese friends ($m=2.81$) and that their friendships did not feel like family ($m=2.87$). IS also indicated that they did not have deep friendships with their Japanese classmates ($m=2.74$). Perhaps most surprising was a somewhat neutral desire, on the part of IS, to make friends with Japanese students. In response to the questionnaire item "I wish I had more Japanese friends", IS responded with a somewhat neutral score of 3.6. This may lend credence to Robinson et al.'s (2020) finding that IS felt intimidated to initiate conversations with host nationals. It may also suggest that IS feel hindered by cultural and linguistic differences. Still, their desire to make Japanese friends ($m=3.6$) was higher than their perceived ability to do so ($m=2.81$).

World Snacks and World Holidays Mixer Events Questionnaires

Two mixer events were held in November and December of 2023. In order to combat issues of belongingness, mattering, and loneliness, our events had 3 goals: 1.) create an environment of IS and DS integration to address issues of belongingness, 2.) create an environment where IS felt welcome and accepted to address issues of mattering, and 3.) create an environment where IS and DS could interact and form relationships to address issues of loneliness. The results of the questionnaire were very positive in terms of addressing these Cycle 1 issues.

Environment of International and Domestic Student Integration

There were many positive takeaways from our mixer event questionnaires. First, both events were attended by both IS and DS, which was an important step for integration. The first event (World Snack Mixer Event) had eight questionnaire responses with almost half (n=3) being IS members. This was a response rate of 61.5% as 13 students attended the event. The second event (World Holiday Mixer Event) also had a somewhat even mix of IS and DS. Of the seven questionnaire responses (response rate=58.3%), three were IS, and four were DS. Additionally, attendees from the first event indicated that they met people from different countries. Seven of the eight attendees (87.5%) selected “strongly agree”. 1 student (12.5%) selected “agree.” None of the students (0%) indicated neutrality or disagreement with this statement.

There was also a positive response to this questionnaire item after the second event. 71.5% indicated that they had met people from other countries, with two participants (28.5%) indicating they had not. It is important to note that the second event employed less researcher-directed structure in order to increase participant talking time. I felt my enthusiasm to engage participants during the first event may have interfered with student engagement, so I chose to approach the second event in a more hands-off manner. This may have backfired in that two students may have stayed within their cliques.

The goal of this integration initiative was to give students a sense of belonging, not only with other international people but also among domestic students. DS comprise 97% of the university demographic so it was important to show IS that they belong among their classmates irrespective of racial and cultural differences. I feel the positive responses to the questionnaire indicate a strengthened sense of interacting and belonging.

Environment Where International Students Felt Welcome and Accepted

Responses to the World Snack and World Holiday mixer events indicate that students felt welcomed and accepted. One of the goals of these events was to impress upon IS that they are seen and matter. In particular, it was important to show students that mattering was not specific to one culture or race. All students should feel like important members of the academic community. Responses to the first event showed unanimous agreement (100%) to the item “This event was inclusive to my culture.” 75% Strongly agreed. The second event also had unanimous agreement with 85.7% strongly agreeing.

Interestingly, in terms of belonging, there was a positive response after the first event to the questionnaire item “I felt at home and accepted at this event.” 87.5% responded to this item with agreement. 62.5% indicated “strongly agree.” One student selected “disagree” but member checking, discussed later, revealed this participant lived alone in Japan and equated “home” with being alone. For this reason, the question was changed to “I felt welcomed and accepted at this event” on the second questionnaire. There was unanimous agreement to this item with 85.7% strongly agreeing.

Environment Where International and Domestic Students Could Interact and Form Friendships

Friendship formation was an important goal of the mixer events as evidence of IS loneliness was prevalent in Cycle 1 data. There was positive questionnaire feedback regarding both friendship-forming and the possibility of friendships continuing. Five attendees at the first event (62.5%) selected either “agree” or “strongly agree” to the questionnaire item “I made friends at this event.” 50% of the

participants selected “strongly agree.” Responses to this question improved for the second event; perhaps the result of fewer researcher-directed activities and more participant talk time. 85.8% responded evenly between “strongly agree” and “agree” to this question after the second event. One participant selected “neither agree nor disagree.”

Additionally, there was some evidence that relationships formed would extend beyond the events. 87.5% agreed to the statement “I will talk to people I met at the event again” after the first event. This positive response remained high after the second event (85.7%). Importantly, participants expressed a desire to engage in future mixer events. There was unanimous agreement after both events to the statement “I will come to future events like this” with 87.5% strongly agreeing after both events. This response is important as it suggests a commitment to reengage with people from different cultural backgrounds. Since Robinson et al. (2020) suggested that international students may feel intimidated to initiate conversations with host nationals, this confidence to reengage in mixer events and conversation is important to our intervention efforts.

Turning Point: Event Effects on International Student Positivity Towards Institution

Perhaps the most encouraging finding was that the mixer events gave participants a more positive feeling about the university in general. Participants agreed unanimously after both events to the questionnaire item “Events like this give me a more positive feeling about this school.” I feel this positive feedback is the result of the intervention’s focus on cultural and racial inclusion for students of various backgrounds; students who have been neglected in the past. I believe these events hosted by the Cultural Awareness Circle sent a message to all students who attended. I believe that message was “Regardless of your background, you have a place here. You matter.” Additionally, participants in Cycle 1 sometimes described domestic students and/or the school as being weird or strange. I feel mixer events offer a turning point for IS to begin harboring more positive feelings regarding their academic environment and their host national classmates.

Exit Interview

There was one student who indicated they had not made friends at the mixer events. I e-mailed this student to inquire if they would be open to an interview. Since this student also participated in Cultural Awareness Circle meetings, I felt they would be a useful source of feedback regarding both action steps. They agreed, and an interview was held on December 22, 2023. I will analyze the data based on the student's pre-intervention experiences, their experiences during intervention, and their outlook moving forward.

Pre-intervention Experiences

There was evidence during the interview that the student participant was experiencing isolation issues prior to intervention. The student participant told the researcher that they were experiencing a lack of social engagement in their university experience. The participant discloses this by stating, "I'm the fourth-year student and in the latest three years I, I just went to class, took the lecture, and went back home." I misunderstood this to mean the student talked with students in their class, but when I asked whether she talked with others in her class, she replied "I did no conversations." This indicated that even in classes full of peers, the student was feeling isolated.

Additionally, there was evidence that the student was experiencing psychological issues as a result of isolation. As the student confides, "I'm depressed. I have developed because of this. I have mental issues. I went to the health place on campus. I took some medicine." This speaks to the Prihadi et al. (2020) finding that feelings of not mattering can lead to low self-esteem, depression, and even suicidal ideation. A student's psychological needs not being met can have highly negative consequences.

This isolation was occurring despite the student's desire to interact with her peers. The student describes this experience by stating, "I want to share my, my daily life with others, and share. I want to ask some others. I can't... have no purpose to. I can't." I found it interesting that this student said they "have no purpose to." This perhaps conveys a belief that the student not only does not belong and is

isolated, but also that they feel they do not matter or have a purpose. It is important to note that the student felt they needed a specific purpose to interact with their classmates.

This reported psychological stress is compounded by the student participant engaging in self-blaming. The student conveys this self-blaming behavior by stating, "I thought I maybe, I was too introverted." When I asked if introversion was an issue prior to coming to this university, the student revealed that it had never been an issue for her in the past. The student went on to say, "Yeah, it's pretty confuse me that whether it is my personality problems, or the, the system's problem. I don't know." It is clear that the isolation this student had experienced was causing her to grapple with questions about her psychological health. This self-blaming behavior comports with Khawaja and Stallman's (2011) findings that IS self-blame in the form of saying they are too shy, modest, or passive.

Prior to intervention, the student participant had engaged in the Campus Mate program. Campus Mate is a student organization tasked with the goal of smoothing the transition IS face moving to a new country. One of the Campus Mate programs is to pair an international student with a domestic student for 20 minutes during lunch. The student participant tells us, "I took an activity they have. Having lunch with the Japanese students once a week for 20 minutes during lunchtime. Yes, but I didn't succeed." Again, I found it interesting that the student said, "I didn't succeed" rather than "the program did not succeed." This perhaps reveals that the student is engaging in self-blaming again. The student participant feels they are to blame for the program's shortcomings and their own resulting isolation.

There was evidence that this program's lack of success was perhaps due to its short length, misguided focus, and failure to continually encourage students to reengage in cross-cultural interaction. The student participant relays the short-length issue to the researcher by saying "It was only for 20 minutes." The operative word for the researcher was "only", indicating the student perhaps wished the interaction had continued longer. The student participant also revealed the misguided focus of the

program, which focused heavily on independent living skills such as cooking, cleaning, and shopping. As the student stated, "I mean I cook... I cook myself", indicating that daily living skills were not an issue.

The participant goes on to relay that belonging and isolation are the real issues she was struggling with. The student reveals this by saying, "It's about how to connect, make friends, and not... independent living is so... not a big problem." Finally, the student participant revealed that the Campus Mate program had failed due to a lack of continued interaction. As the participant states, "After that Japanese people didn't continually uh, connect." This indicates that relations with the domestic student fizzled after the 20-minute intervention, leaving no lasting impact on the student's academic life.

Experiences During Intervention

During the interview, the student participant indicated that the Cultural Awareness Circle and mixer events created a new environment for the student; one where they could interact with their fellow classmates openly. The student conveys this by stating, "I think the Cultural Awareness Circle and mixer events created a very different environment from my daily life any others day... created a new environment." When asked how the student felt during Cultural Awareness Circle and the events, she replied, "I feel I can talk freely."

There was also evidence that the student had a more positive feeling about the host nationals who attended the event. The student participant expressed this by saying, "The people I connect there is very different from the, the normal Japanese people. I think the Japanese people [at the event] are more open." The participant also states, "I think people in the event are more friendly... easy-going." This seems to indicate that the student feels event-going Japanese students are different from typical Japanese students, who she perhaps has a negative feeling toward. This may be the result of a lack of interaction with DS prior to intervention. Intervention may be improving this student's impression of DS. It seems like now she recognizes that not all Japanese people are reserved or unfriendly.

There was also evidence that the event improved the student's confidence to interact with others in the future. The student related this by saying, "Before the event, I saw the university is just the place I took the lecture and I come, and I come back home. It's just this only one function and I don't have connections with others.. pretty lonely. But after that event I... I know I can talk with others." The phrase "I know I can" was particularly encouraging for the researcher. She didn't say "I think I can." She was confident in her new ability to interact with her classmates moving forward. This may be evidence that the impact of intervention may continue beyond the circle meetings and mixer events.

Student Outlook for the Future.

Finally, there was some evidence that the student felt the intervention could not only benefit herself, but also other incoming IS. As the student participant said, "I think the, the event [referring to the mixer event] for me it's good", I asked her how it might benefit other IS. To this question, she replied, "I think positive because uh the foreign students there is nothing... or I didn't see any [events]." When I pressed the student participant on how the event could be improved, she replied "I think it's really good." I feel, from the interview data, that the student had a generally positive impression of our intervention efforts.

Conclusion

It is clear, based on the participant's interview answers, that there were some social and psychological needs not being addressed by the institution. The student reported feeling depressed and seeking medical treatment at the campus health center. The participant blamed themselves by wondering if they were too introverted or had some social or psychological disorder. They let out a relieved laugh when I told them other participants had reported a similar problem. The participant seemed grateful when I suggested perhaps the problem is not entirely uncommon among IS at this institution.

It was interesting that the student described the Cultural Awareness Circle and events as a "new environment." One of my early goals was to establish a safe space for the minority IS at the campus.

The student mentioned that they could talk freely at this event and described the Japanese attendees as more outgoing than usual. Of course, I do not want these relationships to exist only in the confines of this safe space, but perhaps this is the first step to bridge IS and DS interaction and foster improved relations in the future. I hope that this student will feel comfortable engaging in conversations with host national classmates in a natural and organic manner.

This student participant also indicated that interventions such as international clubs and mixer events could have a positive impact on future IS at this institution. The student indicated that there were, prior to our intervention, no events geared at mixing IS and DS. They indicated that if they participated more in these types of events, they would probably make friends. I understood this to mean that the school was not properly addressing the students' social needs prior to intervention. As the student said, most institutional help was in the form of basic daily living skills such as cooking and cleaning. The institution seems to have overlooked a much deeper need; one of being accepted, welcomed, and belonging.

Overall, the Cultural Awareness Circle and mixer events gave the student confidence to interact with their fellow classmates. The student said, "But after that event I, I know I can talk with others." Using the word "know" indicated a level of confidence regarding their newfound ability to interact with their classmates. The student felt the events were not only important for themselves but for other IS. As they indicated, "I think positive because uh the foreign students there is nothing... or I didn't see any [events]."

Section Three: Literature Review

The purpose of this study was to analyze and improve the conditions for international students (IS) at a private four-year research university in Tokyo, Japan. This literature review offers analysis of the existing literature to contextually understand an observed problem of practice within the landscape of available research. There will be three central themes discussed within this literature review.

First, I will examine the treatment of IS at my institution as well as nationally within Japan. I will discuss the low population numbers of IS in Japan and in my institution and discuss government mandates and initiatives aimed at increasing IS in Japan. I will also analyze push/pull factors and how these contribute to brain gain/drain/circulation in the context of a global knowledge economy.

In the second section, I will discuss reasons why, despite government efforts to internationalize, Japan struggles to attract and accommodate IS. In particular, I will talk about competing, and often incongruent, internationalist and nationalistic agendas. I will also discuss teacher competency issues that can contribute to maladaptive approaches. I will explore domestic students' readiness to integrate into more internationalized classrooms. This readiness has to do with passive learning styles and an absence of critical thinking skills, an ability to disagree with "superiors", and a lack of classroom discussions.

In the third section, I will discuss loneliness, isolation, mattering, and belonging as it pertains to IS. Not much research exists exploring these phenomena among IS populations; particularly among international students in Japan. Most of the research I came across dealt with isolation and loneliness in IS populations in America, Australia, and England. As Wawera and McCamley (2020) suggest "There is a small amount of research focusing on loneliness among international students" (p. 1264). I also give an overview of research pertaining to belonging and mattering among university students.

The fourth section will offer some actionable strategies for improving the experiences of IS, as well as improving interactions between IS and DS. This section will explore the implementation of

cultural centers (CC), or groups such as clubs, to make IS feel more at home as a minority group in Japan. CCs can offer a win/win/win situation for IS, DS, and the institution as they help foster a community of multiculturalism, offer a safe space for IS, address the intersectionality of marginalized groups, prepare both DS and IS for a global and multicultural workforce, and increase IS self-esteem and resulting university completion rates. I will propose increasing English as a Medium of Instruction (EMI) programs as well as international and domestic student mixers to increase IS integration in Japanese universities. Although EMI programs could potentially assist IS at other Japanese higher education institutions, it became less of a focus in my research due to the existence of institutional English programs and the lack of students from English-speaking countries. Even though Cycle 1 data informed me that the lack of English programs was not a problem at my specific institution, I still include it in my literature review as I believe it to be an important discussion in regard to international students in non-English-speaking countries.

Finally, I will conclude with a rationale for my research topic as well as questions to address. I will also engage in a discussion of how this study may help IS at my institution, as well as other Japanese higher education institutions. Since my research involved student participants discussing strategies to better accommodate IS, it was important to understand all issues faced by IS in Japanese institutions. These problems potentially included lack of English programs, lack of cultural centers or groups/clubs, lack of mixer events, and/or inadequate teacher training. Students participating in the Cultural Awareness Club could then be informed about the literature and develop research-based strategies for improving the conditions for IS. It is important to note that I did not dictate which strategies the students would employ or which problems they would tackle. I simply discussed the problems and research and let the Cultural Awareness Circle members choose a course of action they felt would benefit IS.

Articles used in this paper were retrieved from Google Scholar, the Northeastern Snell Library, the author's university of employment library, and ProQuest Dissertations and Theses. Some of the keywords used were English as a Medium of Instruction, brain gain/drain/circulation, internationalization of higher education, loneliness, mattering, and belonging.

Transborder Student Migration as a Global Phenomenon

In this section, I will discuss how transborder migration of students is affecting the student demographics globally, nationally, and at the university level. As an overview, I will first discuss IS in Japanese universities. Next, I will provide an overview on how student migration is impacting government programs and higher education institutions. I will discuss push/pull factors impacting transborder migration and discuss multifarious Japanese government efforts and initiatives geared at drawing in international students and staff, increasing classes taught in English, and improving transnational research collaboration.

International Students in Japanese Universities

The increasing phenomenon of transborder studying is a noticeable trend of the new millennium. UNESCO data from 2012 suggests the number of IS globally increased to 3.6 million in the 6 years spanning from 2004-2010, an increase of nearly 50% (Choudaha et al., 2013). The four key countries pulling the lion's share of IS are countries where English is the main language of communication (US, UK, Australia, and Canada) (Choudaha et al., 2013; Lee, 2017). Lee (2017), citing University World News (2012), reveals that the top four international hosting countries draw nearly half (45%) of all global IS. Japan draws 4% of global IS (Lee, 2017).

There is evidence of increasing transborder student mobility to Japan. As Nam & Cheng-Hai (2022) point out, Japan has seen a rapid increase of IS to where they currently represent 5.2% of total higher education enrollment in Japan. As of 2020, the number of IS studying in Japan made it the ninth most popular destination among IS globally (Nam & Cheng-Hai, 2022).

The importance of English in Asian higher education cannot be overstated. Walkinshaw et al. (2017), discussing Kirkpatrick (2010), state that English within the Asia Pacific geographical region has become, by default, the most important language used for commerce, trade, diplomacy, and scholarship. Currently, the largest number of IS migrate to schools in English-speaking countries, particularly the United States, the United Kingdom, Canada, Australia, and New Zealand (Zhang, 2018). As Zhang (2018) clarifies, “most of the non-English-speaking countries have more outbound students than inbound ones” (p. 543). If non-anglophone countries intend to draw IS, they must use the global lingua franca, English, to attract global talent (Mazzarol & Soutar 2002; Shanka et al., 2006; Zhang, 2018). Non-English countries that offer English as a Medium of Instruction (EMI), and English Degree Programs (EDP) have had success internationalizing their higher education institutions (Rose & McKinley, 2018; Shimauchi, 2018).

Access to EMI programs in industrialized nations like Japan is of particular importance considering technological and scientific resources are not globally ubiquitous. Rakhshandehroo (2017), for example, found that Iranian students cited better access to scientific and technological resources as a reason for choosing to study in Japan. These students expressed an interest in staying in Japan after graduating, potentially contributing to brain gain (discussed in further detail below). Briefly, the hypothesis of “brain gain” suggests that, in this modern global knowledge economy, countries benefit from the increase in talented human capital (Batista et al., 2012). Rakhshandehroo (2017) states “The participants listed Japan’s culture and safety record, and high quality of their research fields especially in engineering, as their reasons for their desire to stay in Japan” (p. 45), suggesting access to high-quality research fields as a potential factor in brain gain for Japan.

Government Mandates/Initiatives

The Global 30 Project (G30), on the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sport, Science, and Technology (MEXT) website, commends 13 core universities that “have been implementing a variety of

approaches to internationalize academic systems and campuses such as developing degree programs conducted in English and enriching international student support” (Global 30 Project, n.d.). This program, as well as other initiatives discussed in this section, mainly focused on increasing the number of IS and EMI programs (Aizawa & McKinley, 2020).

In its focus to attract IS, the Japanese government has expressly identified the need for courses taught to non-Japanese students in a language other than Japanese (MEXT, 2013). Shimauchi (2018) suggests that even though English is not specified, courses taught in a medium of instruction other than Japanese implies English. As Shimauchi (2018) suggests, the word for English language courses taught in Japanese schools is “gaikokugo katsudo”, which translates to “other country language.” Essentially, the terms “English” and “foreign language” are somewhat synonymous and used interchangeably with respect to language curriculum.

In 1983, the Japanese Ministry of Education expressed a goal of reaching 100,000 IS by 2020, and quickly completed this goal by 2003 (Nam & Cheng-Hai, 2022). After this success, the government raised the stakes with a new goal to reach 300,000 students by 2020. To help reach this goal, in 2009 the Global 30 project, also known as スーパーグローバル大学創成支援 (Super Global Universities) was implemented and funded 13 top-tier higher education institutions (Nam & Cheng-Hai, 2022). Nam & Cheng-Hai (2022) citing Hennings and Mintz (2015) suggests the goal of this initiative was to promote internationalization in Japanese universities and resulted in “more programs in English, promotion of activities abroad, and an increased number of international students at the 13 universities” (p. 12). The expressed goal of reaching 300,000 IS was also reached early in 2019 (Nam & Cheng-Hai, 2022).

After 2010, Bradford (2019) informs us that the government focused on EMI as a way to create global human resources (global jinzai) in order for future Japanese people to be able to compete in a modern international workforce. In 2012, the Go Global Japan government project focused on giving Japanese students more international experience by encouraging them to go abroad. This project was

followed by the 2014 Top Global University project which also encouraged students to earn credits overseas (Bradford, 2019).

As mentioned in the above paragraph, in 2014 the government initiated the 10-year Top Global University Project (TGUP) for top-tier universities. This initiative gave prospective universities the goal of either becoming leaders in internationalization in Japan or entering the top 100 universities global rankings (Nam & Cheng-Hai, 2022). Universities that are recipients of government funding through this program are required to “increase lectures in English and improve the ratios of foreign faculty and students” (Nam & Cheng-Hai, 2022, p. 12). Aizawa and McKinley (2020) inform us that while programs preceding the TGUP focused on increasing IS and EMI programs in universities, the TGUP also focused on research, in particular research excellence and transnational collaboration.

It is important to note that even universities not receiving funding from the government were compelled to offer EMI due to Japan’s MEXT requirement (Mulvey, 2017). Mulvey (2017) suggests that universities that toed the line regarding accreditation and funding were rewarded with both. Those that did not were punished. As Mulvey (2017) states, by 2014 all Japan’s 85 national universities were under threat of termination if they did not adequately reform. As Mulvey (2017) elucidates, this was a power MEXT did not have prior to this.

Bradford (2019) suggests that all these policies (see Figure 4) were implemented due to pressures from a struggling economy, low birth rates, external international expectations, and a lesser position on the international league tables. Cargill et al. (1996) inform us that Japan experienced an economic boom in the late 1980s, often referred to as the “bubble”, which “burst” leading the economic woes and stagnancy starting from the early 1990s. Low birth rates, which were 2.75 in the 1950s (Raut, 2007), dropped to 1.75 in 1990 and 1.43 in 2017 (Matsuda, 2019), perhaps affected by the bubble burst. These factors, according to Bradford (2019), are two internal factors influencing the Japanese government’s desire to become more international.

Figure 4

Timeline of MEXT Initiatives, Policies, Goals, and Landmarks

Push/Pull Factors & Brain Gain/Brain Drain/Brain Circulation

For clarity, it may be important to define the concepts of brain gain, brain drain, and brain circulation before starting this section. These concepts are important because they give context to student migration patterns, and how these patterns affect global economies and university rankings. Ciumasu (2010) suggests that skilled laborers, or those with bachelor-level degrees, typically move from less-developed countries to more developed ones. The country receiving these skilled laborers are benefitting from “brain gain”, while the country sending skilled laborers are experiencing “brain drain”, or loss of knowledgeable laborers in a global knowledge-based economy. The concept of “brain circulation” arises when an individual from a less developed country pursues an education in a more developed country and then moves back to their country of origin (Ciumasu, 2010). This is sometimes referred to as “reverse brain drain.”

Interestingly, Kapur and McHale (2005) suggest that geographically the migration of laborers tends to be in the direction of South to North, for example, from Africa to Europe. This may lead to

further global inequities between privileged and non-privileged societies. Ite (2002) suggests that this migration pattern is a problem threatening developing countries such as those within Africa.

Countries that host IS are aware of the benefits garnered from attracting and retaining well-educated and trained labor. This is evidenced by special incentives offered to IS by host countries to increase retention of IS in the country after graduation. These incentives include permanent visas and even citizenship (Chan, 2012). Unfortunately, sometimes these overseas-acquired laborers are exploited as cheap labor. Liu-Farrer (2009) highlights a phenomenon known as “side door labor” where well-trained migrant laborers in Japan are poorly compensated due to their non-citizen circumstances.

Governments and institutions, motivated by economic and prestige factors, actively engage in IS recruitment. De Wit (2010) describes a cycle in which increased IS at a higher education institution demonstrates global attractiveness, resulting in higher global ranking, in turn drawing more IS to the institution. This draw of students to a country or institution, whether deliberate or unintentional, is known as push/pull factors (Chan, 2012; De Wit, 2010).

McMahon (1992) found a negative correlation exists between a host country's economic prosperity and international student migration. The correlation is derived from a pattern of migration moving in a vertical flow (from less developed countries to more developed ones). The author suggests that some indirect push/pull may be inherent to a country's global economic position, or even sheer location. Location, for example, may have acted as an indirect pull factor for several offshore medical schools in the Caribbean (Morgan et al., 2017). Economic standing and location are two examples of inherent pull factors not directly related to government or institution manipulation, marketing and/or recruitment efforts.

In addition to inherent pull factors associated with a country or higher education institution, there are direct factors resulting from marketing and recruitment campaigns. Chen (2008) discusses programs aimed at pulling IS to overseas institutions. These programs include joint venture programs,

“twinning” (students complete their degree in a destination country), campus tours, education fairs, and active measures to increase reputational ranking (Chen, 2008). This suggests that the pull factors drawing IS to a host country are not entirely happenstantial, but also the result of campaigning efforts.

Some campaign efforts have even been made to encourage reverse migration of students back to the countries that have been negatively impacted by outward academic migration. This is evidenced by the Vietnamese government’s effort to contact overseas students via online chats. The purpose of these chats was to encourage students to return to their country of origin (De Witt, 2010). This suggests that the impact of brain drain on the Vietnamese economy was enough to warrant proactive government measures to mitigate the adverse effects of brain drain, or loss of skilled laborers.

Ultimately, the picture of transborder migration of IS may depict a zero-sum exchange where one country benefits at the expense of another. Particularly concerning is that the country typically benefitting from the exchange tends to be the more economically developed one, potentially leading to increased global economic disparity. As Japan is an economically developed country, I will consider the impact Japan has on transborder student migration in the following section.

Japan Impact

Moving from the macroscopic global view to the more mesoscopic national view, it is important to consider the ramifications of my research at a domestic level. As my research will potentially impact student migration to Japan, and countries engaging in student exchange with Japan, I need to address the negative and positive impacts of international student import.

Encouraging research regarding Japanese IS exchange comes from Lee (2010) and Yoon et al. (2013). These researchers suggest that reverse migration trends exist between two economically horizontal countries; particularly evidenced in student exchange between Japan and South Korea. As Japan hosts many IS from South Korea (see Figure 5), this suggests some degree of brain circulation between the two countries.

Figure 5

International students in Japan by country (Statista, 2022)

Referring to Figure 5, we can see that the fourth largest demographic of IS in Japan, amounting to roughly 14,250 students, is that of South Korea. Somewhat unsurprisingly, the largest number of IS in Japan are of Chinese origin. This is to be expected as Liu-Farrer (2009) suggests that China is the largest exporter of IS at 14% (p. 183). Perhaps the proximity of Japan as one of the closest developed countries to China contributes to the disproportionate overrepresentation of Chinese students in Japanese universities.

Unfortunately, when considering the literature and how it relates to the current IS demographics in Japan, while there may be some degree of horizontal flow contributing to brain circulation, the overwhelming majority of students are likely to contribute to brain drain for sending

countries. There is also a concern about side door labor exploitation, as many IS come from less economically affluent countries (Liu-Farrer, 2009).

Conclusion

This section has provided the reader with some information regarding the migration trends on IS. A discussion was made regarding how this migration impacts sending and hosting countries. This section also provided the reader with an understanding of national government and local institutions' motivation to draw students. In the next section, I will evaluate some reasons why Japan still struggles, particularly compared to English-speaking countries like England and the US, to attract global academic talent.

Stakeholder Issues Internationalizing Japanese Universities

In this section, I want to discuss issues that arise in Japan's efforts to internationalize its higher education institutions. Aizawa & McKinley (2020) inform us of the levels of stakeholders ranging from the macro (government level), to the meso (institutional level), and the micro (student and teacher level). In this section, I will start with a macro lens and slowly zoom in to the micro.

In this first strand, I will talk about the macro (government) stakeholder level and issues that arise in internationalization efforts. In the second strand, I will zoom in to the meso level (institutional) level. In the third strand, I will talk about the micro (student and teacher level). Finally, I will give some concluding thoughts.

Stakeholder Issues Internationalizing Universities at the Macro Level

Aizawa & McKinley (2020) suggest the breakdown between internationalization efforts in theory and practice may be the result of miscommunication between the stakeholder layers (macro, meso, and micro) of the institution. Aizawa & McKinley (2020) suggest that one such communication breakdown exists regarding the understanding and application of EMI. Lower stakeholder levels, particularly the micro level, may be completely neglected in the decision-making process. As Aizawa & McKinley (2020)

state “decision-making on educational policies is typically dominated by top-bottom management without teacher or student input” (p. 8). Confusion regarding implementation manifests itself as a result of this exclusionary management style. Ali (2013) suggests that even the goal of English in the classroom, whether to teach English language skills or simply teach in English, is unclear. A simple matter such as whether students in EMI classes should actively learn English vocabulary and grammar, or instead use English to discuss course content, is unsettled (Ali, 2013).

Aizawa & McKinley (2020) point out that while MEXT and UNESCO’s definition of EMI expressly state that it does not involve the teaching of the English language, but rather the teaching of course content in English, this may not be clearly understood at the micro level (teachers and students). Galloway et al. (2017), employing a large-scale study, found that nearly half (40%) of Japanese students electing to take an EMI course, did so to improve their English language skills. This suggests that the vision of EMI at the macro level may not be clearly communicated to, or understood correctly, at the micro level.

The motivation to internationalize Japanese universities is also unclear. It is uncertain if the motivation is spurred by a desire to make Japan more international or to spread Japanese ideologies to the outside world. Goodman (2007) describes the Japanese word *kokusai*, or “international”, as being connected to the ideology of strengthening one’s Japanese identity and desire to spread Japanese values to the world. When speaking Japanese, using the word for international (*kokusai*) may have a different meaning and connotation than the English translation, “international.”

Hammond (2016) suggests that some internationalization attempts may have been merely designed to educate outsiders about the uniqueness of Japanese culture. Shimauchi (2018) describes a dichotomous, and perhaps incongruent, desire to be both “cosmopolitan”, or international, while also maintaining nationalist agendas. This notion of international but separate is perhaps a hindrance to creating a truly internationally integrated learning environment. Bradford (2019) supports Goodman

(2007), by suggesting the term “kokusai” itself may have some controversial implications and connections to nationalism; possibly spawned by the rhetoric of former Prime Minister Nakasone.

Shimauchi (2018) goes on to suggest that “EMI programs can be considered as a part of the regime of Japanese soft power diplomacy” (p. 86). The author suggests that these programs are used as a tool to spread Japanese values to the outside world, rather than be inwardly influenced by the international community. Shimauchi (2018) clarifies this point by stating that these programs “empower domestic students to become ‘global human resources’ with ‘Japanese identity’ able to compete with their foreign counterparts while disseminating values and attractiveness of Japanese cultures and products throughout the world” (p. 87).

Hammond (2016) reminds us that in Japan, young students are taught “moral education”, which potentially deepens the sense of nationalism among the people. Moral education classes teach Japanese students about their moral obligation to the country and emperor (Hammond, 2016). The author (Hammond, 2016) supports Shimauchi’s (2018) claim by suggesting that some Japanese internationalism attempts are simply used to educate outsiders regarding the unique qualities of Japanese culture.

Another concern has to do with whether stakeholders at the macro (and possibly meso) level, in their continued efforts to draw IS to Japan, are perhaps taking a somewhat myopic view. That is, they are potentially not fully considering the impact on the micro level, and whether changes best suit the students and teachers. Shimauchi (2018), citing several academics (Hamid et al. 2013; Kirkpatrick 2013; Wilkinson 2013), suggests that the government and higher education institutions, in their effort to draw IS, create globally minded Japanese citizens, and generate revenue, may be prioritizing these aims “ahead of the educational benefits imparted to micro-level stakeholders (students)” (p. 88).

Policy at the macro level could perhaps benefit from clearer goals and objectives. Do stakeholders at this level wish to create globally-minded citizens or spread Japanese values to the outside world? Are these two goals disharmonious? Are EMI programs intended to accommodate IS, or

improve domestic students' English language skills? These are some questions that need addressing at the macro level.

Stakeholder Issues Internationalizing Universities at the Meso Level

In the above section, I took a macroscopic (government and policymaker) view of stakeholder issues. In this section, I will zoom in and focus on the mesoscopic (institutional) issues surrounding internationalization efforts in Japan. I briefly mentioned in the previous section that institutions, in their efforts to market EMI courses and internationalized university environments, may overprioritize these efforts without considering the student (Hamid et al. 2013; Kirkpatrick 2013; Shimauchi, 2018; Wilkinson 2013). Since Japan employs a top-down management style (Aizawa & McKinley, 2020) in decision-making, I will focus on the next rung down (meso) and how decisions at this level trickle down to the micro level.

Tying into this idea of nationalism competing with internationalization efforts at the macro level are the findings of Brown (2014), which suggest a similar confusion exists at the meso level as well. Employing semi-structured interviews of stakeholders across eight Japanese universities, the researcher (Brown, 2014) found that there was a perception that EMI programs might negatively affect the Japanese identity of the university. As one participant reported regarding EMI programs, "I think people would be upset if they thought it [this university] was turning into a foreign university" (Brown, 2014, p. 57). This suggests that English-based courses may be perceived as a threat to the Japaneseness of a university. As Brown (2014) states, "There is a sense among EMI stakeholders that if an EMI programme were to grow too much or become too successful, it could be seen as a threat to the Japanese identity of the university" (p. 56).

In addition to confusion regarding EMI's place in Japanese universities, there is also evidence of insufficient resources to support EMI. NG Chin Leong (2017) found, through semi-structured interviews with four Japanese university deans and language program directors, that although there were

institutional steps taken to prepare for EMI implementation, several factors hindered EMI development and growth. These factors were a deficit in skilled teachers, a lack of motivation and English proficiency among students, an absence of an English-speaking environment, factors pertaining to institutional culture, and misunderstandings among top management.

Available research supports Leong's (2017) findings, suggesting many Japanese universities have a deficit of human resources in the form of competent EMI teachers (Bradford 2013; Brown 2014; Tran et al. 2020; Tsuneyoshi, 2005). Brown (2014) found, through semi-structured interviews over eight Japanese universities, that one perceived reason for EMI's lack of success was due simply to the lack of qualified EMI teachers. NG Chin Leong (2017) found that even when schools wanted to offer EMI they were unable to. As one participant in Leong's (2017) research reported, "We wanted to implement EMI for the whole university but only some teachers can offer EMI classes. Most teachers do not know much about EMI" (p. 64). It is interesting that this participant said teachers are unfamiliar with EMI, rather than they cannot teach in English. It seems more clarity as to what EMI entails needs to come from the government and institutions.

Confirming this lack of EMI clarity is what Dearden (2014) describes as missing guidelines or instruction on how EMI should be implemented in institutions. Dearden (2014) suggests that not only is there a lack of linguistically qualified teachers, but also a lack of resources, standard linguistic requirements for teachers, teaching guidelines, and lack of clarity regarding whether the class should be taught entirely in English, or whether some of the country's L1 should be allowed.

As for macro and meso stakeholder expectations for teachers, as Dearden (2014) states there are no standards in place regarding teacher EMI qualifications. Aizawa and McKinley (2020), citing Aizawa and Rose (2019), found that "at the macro and meso level, TGUP policy guidelines do not explicitly discuss the specific criteria for EMI teachers' linguistic ability, yet expect them to be equipped with sufficient proficiency to deliver courses in English" (p. 13). Bradford (2019) echoes this concern by

suggesting that no benchmarks or requirements for language proficiency are specified for either the teacher nor the student. Bradford (2019) goes on to suggest that research expertise and time abroad are the main considerations when assigning a teacher to an EMI class.

Stakeholder Issues Internationalizing Universities at the Micro Level

In the previous sections, I discussed issues at the macro and meso levels that bleed down to the micro. There tends to be some overlap between the levels, for example, both the macro and meso levels create policies that impact the micro level. Therefore, sometimes it is difficult to discuss one level in a vacuum. In this section, I will be mainly focusing on the micro (student and teacher) level, but I may discuss how the micro is affected by government and management policies such as lack of proper teacher compensation.

Tran et al. (2020) suggests that poor teacher English oral skills contribute to student difficulties. Tran (2020), citing Bradford (2013), found that 80% of students suggested their EMI teacher lacked adequate English pronunciation and vocabulary. Hu (2019) suggests that “without sufficient competence in the medium of instruction, professors are unlikely to engage students in complex cognitive processes, scaffold their effort to master disciplinary knowledge or provide rich language input to develop advanced English proficiency in the students” (p. 8). Again, this may indicate confusion regarding the goal of EMI expressed by MEXT and UNESCO, which is not to develop English proficiency among students, but rather to teach course content in English.

Regarding teaching staff, Tsuneyoshi (2005) suggests that Japanese teachers engaged in EMI teaching require 4 to 5 times more effort to prepare for a class taught entirely in a second language (L2). Teachers in a Bradford (2013) study also expressed concern regarding teaching “dry classes.” In other words, teachers did not feel they were able to use humorous anecdotes or clever cultural references in their teaching. As Bradford (2013) claims, despite the increased difficulty, EMI teachers are rarely compensated adequately. Bradford (2013) and Tsuneyoshi (2005) discussed the need for teachers taking

on the additional arduous task of teaching in their L2 to be properly compensated for their additional efforts. This may increase the desirability of EMI classes among domestic and international staff. It may also increase the quality of EMI classes as extra preparation efforts will be appropriately compensated.

Regarding teacher motivation and curriculum development, there may be a disinterest, or lack of motivation, on the part of teachers to take EMI courses. Bradford (2019) indicates that teacher reluctance makes it difficult to develop an EMI curriculum or provide students with a range of EMI options to choose from. This may hinder the number of EMI courses in a catalogue that IS or domestic students may elect to take. Essentially, not only are teachers unmotivated to teach EMI, but when they do, they are not fairly compensated for their extra effort.

Some researchers suggest that English language deficiency among teachers may simply be a scapegoat, perhaps better explained by poor teacher/student interactions. Bradford (2019) suggests the focus on a teacher's English skills may be overlooking other teaching pedagogies or practices that may better explain the lack of classroom success. Scaffolding and intercultural approaches may be some overlooked factors in successful EMI implementation. Some of the complaints students lodge against teachers seem to suggest additional problems in teaching practice other than simply English skills. Bradford (2019) relays that students complain about "unengaging lessons because the teacher is reading from a pre-written script, a newspaper or PowerPoint slides, or simply displaying information in English [...] while the professor speaks in Japanese" (p. 713). This may suggest teacher practice, not entirely isolated to English skills, perhaps needs some attention.

Further complicating matters is the possibility that teachers may not be amenable to training programs. Bradford (2019) found that teachers at several MEXT-funded universities felt they did not require faculty development (FD) training because their English was good. There was a sentiment among teachers in Bradford (2019) that only teachers with poor English skills needed FD training. Some were surprised that FD training for EMI might not simply focus on the instructor's English skills.

Regarding student readiness, Aizawa and McKinley (2020) suggest that exposure to English-taught classes in secondary education increased students' confidence and preparedness for EMI in university. Additionally, increased awareness and exposure to differences in Western and Eastern teaching styles may be beneficial. Bradford (2013) advances the idea that Japanese students are typically expected to be passive learners who do not question their teachers or peers. This may be a stark difference to Western classrooms that foster critical thinking skills and use discussions as learning tools in classrooms (Bradford, 2013). Perhaps further exposure to Western teaching methods may increase Japanese students' preparedness for EMI courses; an important consideration for Japanese and international student integration.

There is research indicating that discussions play an integral role in English classes (Tsuneyoshi, 2005), and that Western classes tend to use critical thinking skills and discussion as a tool for learning (Bradford, 2013). Western linguistic, educational, and cultural differences, Bradford (2013) suggests, may impede successful EMI implementation. These differences include the implementation of a syllabus and course description, the fostering of critical thinking skills, and the use of discussions as learning tools in classrooms. Japanese students are described as passive learners who do not critically question their teacher or peers (Bradford, 2019). Perhaps teacher training can help teachers foster active learning and discussion in their classes, further exposing students to these teaching styles.

Conclusion

As we move forward towards considering steps for accommodating and integrating increased English classes and IS, the points covered in this section must serve as a guide to act in a prudent manner. In the next section, for example, we will talk about implementing Cultural Centers for minority IS. It is important to consider the friction this may impose on stakeholders with nationalistic goals. We must consider how to create a win/win situation for all stakeholders. I will also consider increasing English-based courses at my institution, so it is essential to bear in mind the readiness of students and

staff for this transition. I will consider how teacher FD training can help teachers increase student interaction, increase student discussion and talk time, and foster critical thinking skills. Finally, I will suggest the incorporation of IS and domestic student mixers, exposing domestic students to English and improving friendship-building for both domestic and IS. Again, it is important to consider how these steps will not only benefit one stakeholder group but all members of my institution.

International Student Isolation and Loneliness

A few research studies exist exploring loneliness and isolation among IS in England, Australia, and America. This research will create context and inform the action steps that follow this section. Since the research is relatively sparse, I will organize the research I found into three sections based on the country of research, 1.) America, 2.) Australia, and 3.) England. I could not find any research about IS isolation and loneliness in Japan.

International Student Isolation and Loneliness in Australia

Sawir et al (2008), explored feelings of isolation and loneliness across 200 IS in Australia. The researchers employed intensive interviews to better understand these students' experiences. Of the 200 participants interviewed, two-thirds described experiencing problems related to loneliness and isolation. These experiences were deeply felt immediately after arriving at the host university. The researchers put feelings of loneliness expressed by IS into three categories: 1.) Personal loneliness, 2.) Social loneliness, and 3.) Cultural loneliness. Personal loneliness had to do with losing contact with friends and family. Social loneliness resulted from a loss of social networks. The third form of loneliness, cultural loneliness, was brought on by the lack of linguistic and cultural connections.

Khawaja and Stallman (2011) examining 22 international students in an Australian university found that most of these students reported experiencing loneliness and social isolation. The researchers suggested that many of the difficulties with isolation and loneliness had to do with a lack of friendship formation with domestic students. The research suggested that IS in this study were unable to form friends with domestic students despite a desire to. The participants responded that they not only had

difficulty forming friendships but also had minimal interaction with domestic students. The students sometimes placed the blame on themselves by describing themselves as too shy, modest, or passive.

Arkoudis et al. (2019) found that while IS report high feelings of satisfaction overall on questionnaires, deep exploration in focus groups revealed feelings of social isolation and lack of belongingness. The researchers conclude, “assuming that international and domestic student interactions will occur naturally is proving to be ineffective” (p. 811). They suggest that proactive approaches need to be taken in order to increase IS and DS interactions, including increasing IS and DS cultural literacy, and giving IS “greater insights into their host cultures so they can have the confidence to interact more with their domestic classmates” (p. 811). They also recommend raising awareness about this issue with teachers and staff through training efforts to sensitize them to the problem.

International Student Isolation and Loneliness in America

Girmay and Singh (2019) employing a narrative case study of ten international graduate students in America found that all the participants reported feelings of isolation and loneliness in the host university. Furthermore, IS isolation and loneliness led to feelings of perceived xenophobia and insincerity when domestic students attempted to make connections. Participants reported feeling depressed and losing interest in forming friendships with domestic students or joining campus events. This, over time, only aggravated the problem.

Erichsen and Bolliger (2011) using a mixed methods approach employing surveys and focus groups found that IS experienced high levels of isolation during both online classes and traditional classroom settings. IS taking online courses reported even greater feelings of isolation than those in traditional classrooms. Interestingly, participants in this study offered suggestions for how to decrease feelings of isolation among IS. These suggestions included events such as buddy systems, informal lunches with students and staff, seminars, and orientation events.

Trice (2007) examined IS isolation from the perspective of faculty members. The researcher interviewed 27 faculty members, including both foreign-born and American-born. The researcher found

that the faculty members believed that IS were not well integrated into the university community. These members noted that IS and DS did not study together or spend time socially. The participants believed the reason for poor integration was the desire for IS to stay within their own cultural groups. The general consensus was that IS chose isolation, and described this phenomenon in a somewhat negative manner. One American-born faculty member, for example, suggested that Korean students had their own Mafia. Another foreign-born faculty suggested that Korean and Chinese students stuck together to the point of self-detriment.

International Student Isolation and Loneliness in the UK

Wawera and McCamley (2020), looking at IS experiences in a UK university, found that three out of four IS were negatively affected by loneliness and isolation. The researchers discovered that loneliness and isolation were negatively correlated with the use of student support services. Essentially, the students who used the student support services were able to improve their social networks. Interestingly, IS from India and Japan reported knowing about the support services but not using them because “they felt that too many ‘strangers’ attended certain activities” (p. 1269). This is contrasted by other non-Japanese and non-Indian respondents who felt the events were too small and wanted more members in attendance.

IS Belonging and Mattering

Van Horne et al.(2018) issued surveys to students in nine American universities and found that IS reported feeling less socially satisfied than their domestic counterparts. IS in this study reported feeling less welcomed and respected when compared to other students at the universities. As the authors (2018) note, “International students were less likely to believe that there was a positive climate for diversity and respect on university campuses” (p. 361). García et al. (2019) found that IS were more likely to form bonds with instructors and administrative staff than with DS. These interactions with staff offered IS a strategy for feeling that they belonged. Additionally, the authors found that students who felt they belonged were less likely to withdraw.

This feeling of not belonging, among IS, may be particularly strong in societally homogenous countries. International students in a Northern Ireland university perceived the university as having “an unwelcoming learning environment and a lack of interest from domestic peers” (Cena et al., 2021, p. 819). The authors (2021) suggest that even small cultural insensitivities made IS feel unwelcomed and disrespected. The authors, discussing an incident where DS had trouble understanding a Chinese accent, noted, “Small incidents make students feel unrecognized and unaccepted, as opposed to an integral part of the campus environment.” It may be important to be aware of these cultural microaggressions and/or microtransgressions and consider how they impact IS sense of belonging within the institution.

Regarding mattering, there was very little research regarding this phenomenon as it pertains to international students. However, some research did exist regarding the impact of mattering on the psychological health of university students in general. Prihadi et al. (2020) suggested that a sense of mattering has a protective effect against suicidal thoughts in university students. The authors summarize their research by stating, “Individuals with higher levels of mattering were reported to have lower severity of suicide ideation” (p. 500).

Flett et al. (2021) found that feelings of not mattering among university students led to depression and self-criticism. This self-criticism included feelings of self-hate. Conversely, the researchers found that sensing that one mattered led to more positive feelings among university students. As the researchers state, “mattering was positively associated with reassured self, and negatively associated with inadequate self and hated self” (p. 1305). This suggests that not mattering can lead to unfavorable opinions of self among students, while mattering could potentially increase positive views regarding self-image.

Conclusion

While the research on IS loneliness, isolation, belonging, and mattering was relatively sparse, existing data suggests that the phenomenon is experienced across several continents, perhaps

irrespective of the host country or IS country of origin. There is evidence that social isolation and loneliness result in IS potentially harboring negative feelings towards DS and even potentially negative feelings towards IS from domestic people. There is also evidence that mattering and belonging play important roles in students' image of self and sense of being welcomed in the academic community.

Best Practices

In this section, I plan to discuss actionable strategies for better accommodating IS and domestic students in an increasingly internationalized university setting. As mentioned in the previous section, it is important to create a win/win situation where all stakeholders, both domestic and international, benefit from applied change. This research conducted in this literature review was intended to inform the researcher and participants about potential problems IS face, and together strategize research-based actionable intervention strategies.

In the first strand of this section, I will propose the implementation of cultural centers or clubs. This, as I will explain in further detail, is an example of a win/win/win as it provides IS a win with the formation of a safe space (Boyd, 2016), gives the institution a win by showing its dedication to multiculturalism (Jenkins, 2008), and is a win for domestic students in that it prepares them for the emerging multicultural global workforce (Poch et al., 2012).

In the second strand, I will advocate for increased courses taught in English. Again, I will attempt to frame this discussion as a win/win/win/win. I will argue that increasing English-based lessons is in line with several government policies and goals (Aizawa & McKinley, 2020), amounting to a political win. I will also discuss how such courses are a win for the university in terms of increased prestige, research output, and ranking (Coleman, 2006; Deem et al., 2008; De Wit, 2010; McAleer et al., 2019). Additionally, I will discuss how this change could potentially benefit DS and IS by increasing domestic students' English competency skills, accommodating IS learner needs, increasing scholarship and research collaboration, and improving job opportunities (Aizawa & McKinley, 2020; Bradford, 2013).

In the third strand, I will discuss the importance of intercultural mixer events. For the purposes of this paper, the author defines an intercultural mixer event as an event taking place on campus where international and domestic students can get together to build friendships and academic networks. A gap exists in research pertaining to mixer events and the impact on IS in Japanese universities, but I feel we can learn from the success American institutional counterparts have had integrating IS with their domestic students.

Finally, in the fourth strand, I will discuss the need for faculty training to improve EMI classes by making them more interactive, discussion-based, and fostering student critical thinking skills (Bradford, 2013). As discussed above, there may be a sense among EMI teachers that English skills are the only requirement to teach EMI courses (Bradford, 2019). As frequent student complaints, addressed in the previous section, pertained to non-interactive courses (Bradford, 2019), I will discuss how training could potentially remedy this problem.

Helping Establish International Cultural Centers or Clubs

While the research on Cultural Centers (CCs) or clubs in higher education is relatively sparse, I intend to discuss what is available in the literature and connect this knowledge to my institution. In this section, I will focus on how CCs have been applied in the United States, and some potential benefits attested to by the respective academics. Since American and Japanese higher education institutions are vastly different, the knowledge available is perhaps not generalizable. Still, it can be assumed that some experiential knowledge generated in American institutions is transferable, and thus can better inform practice in Japanese institutions.

Dedication to Multiculturalism

“I feel we’re a bit ignored” (Amil, Cycle 1 Interview, 2022)

A significant reason to implement a CC is that it sends a message to marginalized populations, affirming the institution’s position as standing together with these groups. Jenkins (2008), in their paper

regarding the Paul Robeson Cultural Center at Penn State, suggests CCs are “the most viable venues through which an institution’s commitment to diversity can be demonstrated” (p. 25). Considering the evidence of neglect appearing in the Cycle 1 data, CCs and cultural spaces such as clubs and circles, may be an opportunity for the institution to recommit to these valuable students.

Princes (1994) echoes this sentiment by suggesting that supplying provisions to immigrant or minority students is “magnanimous”, and “laudable.” Davenport (2013) goes on to suggest that CCs not only promote community and cultural identity but also make the students feel like they matter. Given that students belonging to an underrepresented demographic may feel lost or unimportant, the institution’s commitment to instilling a sense of mattering to these students is essential. Research suggests that CCs may positively impact students’ sense of belonging (Welch, 2008), and mattering (Toya, 2011).

Creating a Safe Space for International Students

“...but for many [IS] for instance, it's kind of hard to make friends” (Fredo, Cycle 1 Interview, 2022)

Safe spaces can refer to bodily safety, as when students are violently targeted based on their differences but can also refer to psychological safety. Regarding non-violent discrimination, there may exist a belief that talking about or even acknowledging racial and ethnic differences is impolite. Ludlow, (2004) suggests that people are taught to pretend to be color-blind or impervious to racial and ethnic differences. Ludlow (2004) describes this privileged “distancing game” where members of “dominant groups have been ‘taught not to see’” (p. 41). Citing, Wildman and Davis (1996), Ludlow (2004) notes “Being a member of a dominant group allows me to ignore both my own dominance and the experiences of members of the non-dominant groups” (p. 41). Boyd (2016) suggests CCs offer students a place to safely discuss the topic of difference. This may be beneficial for the dominant group, as well as the marginalized group.

CCs also offer students a space to network with other marginalized students. By commingling with members of similarly marginalized groups, students of a minority group may feel less isolated. This sense of belonging, presumably, has an important psychological impact. McDowell and Higbee (2014), discussing the University of Minnesota's commitment of an entire university floor for a cultural center, suggest these spaces offer a home-away-from-home for marginalized students. This may be particularly important for transborder students, who find themselves thousands of miles away from their home countries.

Addresses Intersectionality of Students

"...stuff that the university themselves have, have done towards me, I will say that it's not like they make it easier" (Fredo, Cycle 1 Interview, 2022)

Crenshaw (2015) was the first to use the phrase "intersectionality" to describe situations where people belong to several minority and/or marginalized groups. Consider, for example, a female international student who also identifies as queer. In this case, the student may be marginalized and oppressed for being IS, female, and/or queer. CCs offer support to students who are facing cultural battles on multiple fronts (Clauson & McKnight, 2018; Harris & Patton, 2017). Baudinette (2016) discusses how xenophobia in Japan extends beyond national identity but is also experienced by members of the LGBTQ+ community. It is possible to imagine the struggle of a gay or transgender student who feels open and accepted in their country of origin, reexperiencing discrimination in a new country. This student may feel they need to "come out" a second time in a new environment that may not be entirely welcoming.

Hypolite (2020) discusses how a black cultural center (BCC) at Western Coast University addresses intersectionality by having Asian American, LGBTQ+, and Latinx "cultural and identity centers all located in the same building" (p. 52). Hypolite (2020) discusses a program known as Cultural Mix which seeks to collaborate efforts between the university's centers to discuss social issues and gain a

better intersectional perspective. Hopefully, CCs, and/or cultural clubs, at Japanese institutions can also serve students by addressing and acknowledging the intersectionality of students' identity.

Preparing Students for a Global Workforce

Poch et al. (2012) suggest that universities must expose students to cultural diversity to increase students' intercultural competency and prepare them for employment in the modern diverse workforce. As Poch et al. (2012) point out, employers are calling for "higher education to better support graduates' development of the capacities to work productively and positively within professional environments of diverse cultures, views, and opinion" (Call for International Skills section, para. 3). Cheesman et al. (2008) indicate that CCs do in fact foster and contribute to a better sense of cultural awareness among students, adding to their intercultural competency.

It is important to note that CCs and cultural clubs at Japanese institutions would not only benefit marginalized groups, but also benefit domestic students. As Japanese students enter an increasingly culturally diverse workforce, they will require experience working and problem-solving with people of various cultural backgrounds. CCs and cultural clubs, through meetings and events, offer both IS and domestic students exposure to people of multifarious cultural backgrounds. It is important to promote this win/win scenario to potential stakeholders.

Increase Student Self-Esteem and Completion Rates

"One foreign student in four actually ends up repeating the year" (Fredo, Cycle 1 Interview, 2022)

Minority groups struggle more than non-minority students when it comes to integrating into the university environment (Stovall, 2000). The most critical determiner of student persistence is their interactions during the first half-year of college (Stovall, 2000; Tinto, 1994, 1996). Chiang (2020) suggests that campus centers "serve students with different minority identities by providing both a safe space for these students as well as cultural validation" (p. 1183). Chiang (2020) is using the idea of

cultural validation to advocate for centers geared toward students with disabilities. Again, this connects to the intersectionality (Crenshaw, 2015) of academic environments.

Maramba and Palmer (2014), speaking about cultural validation experienced by Southeast Asian American students in cultural centers, suggest these students needed to feel they were supported and belonged. Maramba and Palmer (2014) further add to this by stating these students were seeking “a home away from home” (p. 525). This sense of needing to belong, be validated, and feel at home is essential for all students. As one black student in a predominantly white institution states, “We feel that were a guest in someone else’s house” (Turner, 1994, p. 356). Turner (1994) suggests that graduation rates are lower for students of color than for white students. The goal of cultural centers and clubs should be to make students feel more like valuable members of the community, rather than guests. This feeling of belonging, particularly at the outset of the student’s university experience, is essential to academic success.

Increase English as a Medium of Instruction Courses

Before addressing the need for EMI in Japanese universities, I feel it is important to briefly discuss some dangers imposed by prescribing English to global institutions. I will discuss some concerns regarding linguistic and cultural imperialism that EMI poses. I will finally argue that despite these genuine concerns, English is an undeniable global lingua franca and therefore an important language for academic collaboration and transnational research. I hope after reading this section, the reader will come away understanding that the benefits of EMI instruction perhaps outweigh the consequences. At the very least, English is an undeniable global force in higher education and academia. At the culmination of this section, I will discuss the benefits of EMI and internationalization for stakeholders in higher education institutions. Again, I will frame these benefits in terms of multiple wins for all stakeholders.

The concepts of internationalization and EMI are coiled together in such a way that, often, it is difficult to discuss them separately. Aizawa and McKinley (2020) even suggest that the two concepts are so interwoven that EMI is sometimes unambiguously referred to by academics as the “Englishization” of higher education; often with a negative connotation. Kirkpatrick (2011) suggests that the need to Englishify higher education has negative consequences on global scholarship, local languages, and also pushes Anglo-Saxon viewpoints on the rest of the world. I do not intend, in this paper, to refute claims that English, and specifically linguistic homogenization, may have negative cultural and anthropological consequences. I have personally published papers about the homogenization of global languages and discussed at some length the negative consequences on cultural identity and language death (Sakellarios & Burton, 2017; Sakellarios & Egitim, 2021).

Some academics have even suggested that English is a “killer language” (Coleman, 2006). These concepts perhaps extend beyond the scope of this paper. For the purposes of this paper, I accept that English is widely regarded as a global lingua franca and global contact language (Canagarajah, 2006; Coleman, 2006; Jenkins & Leung, 2014; Seidlhofer, 2005) and an important language of academia and transnational research (Coleman, 2006). Even Kirkpatrick (2011), who warns of the dangers of Englishization, also contends that the benefits of internationalization are apparent, in that it fosters staff and student exchange and general academic cooperation.

Regarding the undeniable global force and impact English has had, Coleman (2006) likens English as a teaching medium to the “Microsoft effect.” This effect describes a situation where one medium becomes so powerful that discussing the viability of other mediums becomes meaningless. This effect, the author suggests, is true of English. The authors suggest that perhaps the world is moving towards a form of bilingualism where one language relates to cultural identity, and the other to global affairs. Reviewing several studies (Brown, 2005; Hoare, 2001; Tannenbaum & Howie, 2002; Uzawa,

2019), Sakellarios and Egitim (2021) affirm that a correlation exists between the dominant language and a sense of national identity.

Regarding Japan, Shimauchi (2018) suggests that, unlike other non-English speaking countries in Europe and other parts of the world, Japan never experienced colonization from another empire. As a result, Shimauchi (2018) suggests this has left Japan in its own sphere culturally and linguistically. Shimauchi (2018) suggests this as a possible reason Japanese universities are somewhat uniform linguistically and demographically. Typically, the majority of students in Japanese higher education are of Japanese origin, and the language spoken is Japanese (Shimauchi, 2018). For this reason, EMI may be important to break the linguistic monopoly of Japanese in Japan's higher education institutions.

Tsuneyoshi (2005) asserts that despite claims of linguistic and cultural imperialism made by some academics, English is undeniably the language of global politics, economy, and technology. Speaking on the importance of English in the academic world, Tsuneyoshi (2005) says, "The major scientific journals, the world publishers, and major world funding organizations tend to be located in, or influenced by, specific industrialized countries, and tend to use world languages, the prime language being English" (p. 66). Tsuneyoshi (2005) goes on to suggest that the Japanese government supports the use of English in higher education as a means to comport with global demands. Tsuneyoshi (2005) highlights a 1997 government report supporting the use of English in higher education for the following reasons:

In order to lessen the burden of having to learn Japanese for prospective international students, and to provide to many high-achieving foreign students an opportunity to study in Japan, it is important to establish educational programs using foreign languages (primarily English). It is also important for Japanese students, in addition to foreign students, to participate in these programs. (p. 67)

This government report suggests a recognition of the benefits internationalization will provide multiple stakeholders; particularly from the addition of “high-achieving” foreign students. This is in line with research suggesting that international student and staff demographics positively impact the Times Higher Education (THE) global ranking (McAleer et al., 2019) and the citation index, which is a system that ranks universities based on the number of English-language publications (Shimauchi, 2018). Essentially, a university with more English-speaking academics will, presumably, produce more English-based research, positively impacting the institution’s ranking. Therefore, increasing international students and staff poses a win/win for the government in the form of increased skilled laborers, or brain gain and brain circulation, (Batista et al., 2012; Ciumasu, 2010; Ioannidis, 2004; Ite, 2002; Kruanak & Ruangkanjanases, 2014; Lee & Kim, 2010; Michaelis, 1990; Saxenian, 2002; Yoon et al, 2013) as well as a win for the institution which stands to climb in global ranking, in turn attracting more students (McAleer et al., 2019).

Regarding a win/win for domestic students and international students, increased exposure to English benefits domestic students seeking employment. As Aizawa and McKinley (2020) posit, “Although we need more empirical evidence about improved job opportunities for domestic students via EMI, we agree that improving domestic students’ English proficiency should lead to enhanced career opportunities as envisaged by the Japanese government’s objectives” (p. 2). Essentially, it is hard to imagine that, in a world where English is an accepted lingua franca (Canagarajah, 2006; Coleman, 2006; Jenkins & Leung, 2014; Seidlhofer, 2005) increasingly used in transnational scholarship, trade, and commerce (Coleman, 2006; Kirkpatrick, 2010; Walkinshaw et al., 2017) English language skills would not impact job acquisition and security. There is research showing that domestic students studying in English alongside IS benefited in terms of language development (Bradford, 2013; Galloway et al., 2017; Phuong & Nguyen, 2019).

Regarding the win for IS and domestic students, it is important to integrate the two demographics when streaming students into classes. Morita (2012) found, through the use of surveys, that English-taught classes can attract IS, but these classes tend to be segregated to IS; lacking a domestic Japanese presence. The researchers found that very few Japanese students take English-taught classes, creating an academic environment exclusive to IS. EMI implementation needs to consider integrating IS and domestic students, which could in turn benefit both stakeholder parties by helping IS feel they belong and matter (Toya, 2011; Welch, 2008) and domestic students by preparing them for multicultural interactions in the modern workforce (Poch et al., 2012)) and may improve their English skills (Bradford, 2013; Galloway et al., 2017; Phuong & Nguyen, 2019)).

Finally, regarding the impact on IS learner needs and expectations, Rakhshandehroo (2017) suggests that Iranian students in Japan expressed a desire to study in English. The participants in Rakhshandehroo's (2017) study reported dissatisfaction regarding lack of English in many classes, seminars, and meetings. Some students were led to believe, through prior exchange with their supervisors, that they would not need Japanese language at their university. This suggests that some IS require, and perhaps expect, English to be provided to better accommodate their learner needs.

International & Domestic Mixers

The research in this paper follows the grounded theory framework of Glaser & Strauss (2017). Grounded theory, as Glaser and Strauss (2017) put it, "is derived from data and then illustrated by characteristic examples of data" (p. 5). Noble and Mitchell (2016) explain that Grounded Theory (GT), is an approach to research where theory generation is data-driven, or grounded in the data, allowing the researcher to collect and analyze research simultaneously.

Following this approach, I began collecting data before realizing that international and domestic student lack of interaction was an issue. As I began collecting data through surveys, I began to uncover an image of IS as isolated and disconnected from domestic students. Many students related to me that

there were little-to-no events for IS that included domestic students, even though participants relayed a desire for these kinds of events. Events for IS were, according to Cycle 1 data, poorly attended by domestic students. The result is that some IS at this institution felt they did not have many domestic friends or contacts outside the classroom or labs. One student from Africa conveyed to me that the problem was so severe that after their classes finished, the student just went home to his apartment and waited for their next class to start. It was because of this student specifically that I wanted to address this issue as a focused action step in my research.

While a gap exists in the research regarding Japanese and IS interaction and resulting satisfaction and retention rates, I would like to reference some research existing in other parts of the world. Hopefully, this data will be indicative of human nature and the importance of human bonds. Trice (2004) cites a study conducted by Westwood and Barker (1990), who found that IS who were involved in an 8-month pairing program with domestic students had better grades and higher retention rates than their counterparts who were not involved in the program. Perrucci and Hu (1995) found, through multiple regression analysis, that contact with domestic US students was one of the main determinants of student satisfaction. The other two determiners were language skills and perceived discrimination. It is perhaps somewhat intuitive that a person feeling as though they belong, or are part of an inclusive learning environment, could have some positive psychological effects.

This intuitive sense of human nature could be, as Trice (2004) suggests, indicative of Social Capital Theory (Stanton-Salazar, 1997). The theory of social capital, originated from the work of Bourdieu (1986) and Putnam (2002). Siisiainen (2003) clarifies that social capital has three components: “moral obligations and norms, social values (especially trust) and social networks (especially voluntary associations)” (p. 183). Trust in one’s community and social networks builds a healthy culture and the symbolic currency of social capital (Putnam et al., 1992). Racism and social issues in the United States have, for example, negatively affected social capital. As Putnam et al. (1992) state, “[...] in some modern

countries — in America's urban ghettos and suburbs, for example — the last several decades have witnessed a silent erosion of social capital” (p. 34).

The concept of social capital gives us a lens with which to view research indicating social bonds with domestic students have positive effects on IS. Abe et al. (1998), for example, found, through questionnaires, that IS involved in peer programs scored higher on adjustment markers than non-participating respondents. Surdam and Collins (1984) found through questionnaires that more interaction with Americans (domestic students) was associated with better IS adaption. Abe et al. (1998), citing Yang et al. (1994) found through survey analysis that the biggest hindrance to meaningful relationship with domestic students was “lack of opportunity to interact socially” (Abe et al., 1998, p. 539).

Creating inclusive mixer events may be one way to increase social interaction opportunities for DS and IS. Considering the win/win/win/win situation, this interaction is a win for the country as it contributes to higher retention and graduation rates, potentially resulting in knowledge economy brain gain/circulation (Batista et al., 2012; Ciomasu, 2010; Ioannidis, 2004; Ite, 2002; Kruanak & Ruangkanjanases, 2014; Lee & Kim, 2010; Michaelis, 1990; Saxenian, 2002; Yoon et al, 2013). It is a win for the institution as it may increase its attractiveness to IS, resulting in improved global rankings (McAleer et al., 2019). It is a win for domestic students as interaction with IS may improve their English skills (Bradford, 2013; Galloway et al., 2017; Phuong & Nguyen, 2019) and prepare them for multicultural interactions in the modern global workforce (Poch et al., 2012). It is also a win for IS in that it could potentially improve their grades and retention rates (Westwood & Barker, 1990), improve their adjustment and adaption to a new academic environment (Surdam & Collins, 1984; Yang et al., 1994), and increase their symbolic sense of social capital (Putnam et al., 1992; Stanton-Salazar, 1997).

Although I did not find many empirical studies about the effects of mixer events, I did find some anecdotal evidence reported by universities employing mixer events. Ene (2021) reported that Indiana

University-Purdue University Indianapolis (IUPUI), in an effort to fight IS isolation, employed events aimed at intercultural exchange between IS and domestic students. As Ene (2021) reported “we organized a speed friending event for 12 international and domestic students, who assessed the event as excellent or very good. Thus, we learned that, if opportunities for intercultural engagement were created, students would attend” (p. 2). Reporting on subsequent larger mixer events that involved students, staff, and administrators at IUPUI, Ene (2021) suggested that high attendance rates confirmed the success of such events and gave students an opportunity to discuss intercultural matters in a casual, informal setting.

Li et al. (2018) discussed how the University of Colorado, Boulder used the campus library space for programs aimed at enhancing domestic and IS interaction. The library allocated space for several international student events, including an international photo contest, a speed friending event, and a talent show. As the authors (Li et al., 2018) attested, “These programs allow international and domestic students to connect with each other and the global community, to explore cultural heritage in a safe environment, and to build and renew their social capital” (p. 3).

Increasing Faculty Development Training

As mentioned above in the “Stakeholder Issues Internationalizing Universities at the Micro” section”, some teachers may struggle to provide students with interactive lessons. Bradford (2019) describes the often-cited complaint of students who feel unengaged by teachers reading scripts, PowerPoint slides, or simply providing the students with a piece of information in English, and then explaining it in Japanese (Bradford, 2019). This suggests pedagogical issues outside the teacher’s English language ability. Perhaps some EMI teachers are not properly equipped to supply the students with interactive lessons.

As I plan to engage in Action Research, I would not unilaterally design a training program for EMI teachers but rather do so with the help of a team of participants. I would, however, suggest that there is

a lot of research indicating that interaction is an essential aspect of successful EMI classes (Ismailov, 2022; Mackey, 2013). Ismailov (2022) offers us a working definition of the pedagogical approach of interaction in EMI as follows:

Prolonged or episodic topic-based verbal exchange between a content lecturer and students, and to a lesser extent between students themselves, aimed at the production of meaningful content knowledge in English and its effective comprehension in a multilingual classroom environment. (p. 2)

This tells us that a class involving interaction is not one where the teacher is talking while the students are passively learning. This differs from the passive learning style Bradford (2019) tells us that Japanese students are used to and expect.

A concerning assertion by An et al. (2021) is that using a second language (L2) to teach leads to more monologic classes with less student involvement. This may be counterproductive when we consider what An et al. (2021) say regarding active and interactive learning “Higher quantities of student talk reflect more student participation in classroom interaction and can thus indicate more opportunities for language learning and science learning” (p. 8). In fact, research involving more than 1,700 students in EMI courses in 18 countries indicated that noninteractive and monologic learning was more frustrating for students than language proficiency deficits (Ismailov & Yamamoto, 2021).

One thing to consider when training teachers to design more interactive lesson plans is what kinds of questions the teacher is asking students. Llinares et al. (2012) suggests there are two types of questions a teacher can ask their student: display questions and referential questions. As the authors (2012) note, “Display questions are those whose answer is known by the questioner, while referential questions seek information unknown to the teacher” (p. 84). Llinares et al.’s (2012) research findings suggest that referential questions invoked longer, more complex answers from students, and thus may be better suited for interaction-style EMI classes.

Another possible consideration when designing an EMI class with the goal of increasing interaction is the Initiation/Response/Follow-up approach (IRF) (Mehan, 1979). This approach is a turn-taking sequence where a conversation is initiated by either the student or teacher, to which a response is provided, to which either another response is given, or feedback is issued (Miao & Heining-Boynton, 2011). A simple 3-turn IRF might be as follows:

Teacher: When did Columbus sail the ocean blue? (Initiation)

Student: 1492. (Response)

Teacher: Nice job! (Follow-up)

The initiation in this 3-turn IRF employs a display question, where the teacher expects a specific answer. A more complex and Socratic IRF sequence employing a referential initiation question might go as follows:

Teacher: Do you think it was good that Columbus came to America? (Referential Initiation)

Student: Yes. (Response)

Teacher: Why do you think that? (Follow-up)

Student: Because he was the first person to go there? (Response)

Teacher: Was he the first person there? (Follow-up)

Student: I don't know. Was he? (Response)

Miao & Heining-Boynton (2011) found that IRF, particularly if mixed with a Response to Intervention (RTI) where a teacher reflects on their teaching to provide customized and improved teaching to the student, had a positive effect on student learning and also increased student talk time. With participating members of my action research plan, I would like to explore possible methods to

make EMI classes more interactive, improving the quality of instruction and learning experience for students.

Conclusion/Best Approaches

This section focused on actionable steps for improving internationalization efforts at Japanese universities. In particular, I considered strategies that would amount to a win/win/win/win for all stakeholders involved. Any action that only benefits one demographic may find resistance from another group that feels excluded. For this reason, I considered how change would impact the macro, meso, and micro (Aizawa & McKinley, 2020) layers of the institution and create benefits for all parties involved.

Applying grounded theory (Glaser & Strauss, 2017) to initial data, I suspected that this specific institution, one where IS are predominantly from non-English-speaking countries, could potentially benefit from change in the form of cultural centers or clubs that create safe spaces for IS as well as intercultural dialogue between IS and domestic students. I envisaged this as fostering communication and preparing both parties for multicultural interactions in today's modern workforce. Finally, based on cycle 1 data, I proposed mixer events based on US universities that appear to have had some success in this approach. The participants I communicated with said that current international student events are typically unattended by domestic students. Together with participants, it may be beneficial to develop strategies to increase domestic student attendance and help bridge the cultural gap between IS and Japanese students.

Summary

This literature review has created an overview of current policies and practices in the realm of internationalization of Japanese universities. Issues at various stakeholder levels were discussed to uncover culprits for hindered internationalization efforts in higher education institutions. These hindrances included unclear government policy, expectations, lack of clear definitions, lack of guidelines, lack of qualified teachers, lack of English-speaking environments, lack of incentives, unclear institutional

policies and expectations, cultural differences in teaching/learning styles, and perceptions regarding teacher training being unnecessary.

As my research employs Action Research methods, I discussed with participants some strategies to foster a better international environment for both domestic and international students. The suggestions I made to participating members are included in the literature review. These action steps are, I believe, supported by research and may be conducive to building a more accommodating international atmosphere at this institution. All research-based approaches outlined in the literature review were discussed with participants. Based on Cycle 1 data I made suggestions for appropriate action steps to participants involved in Cycle 2 change agency. These steps included establishing cultural centers and/or clubs for domestic and international students providing casual and safe interaction. This center or club could, I believed, also host international and domestic student mixers for networking and friendship building. It was my hope that these research-based approaches would improve the atmosphere of cultural inclusivity at my institution.

Section Four: Contextualization

This chapter contextualizes the Action Research findings within the literature. I will open with a brief description of the purpose of the research and a restating of the research questions for reference. Next, the context of the research, a Japanese private university, will be described; including a discussion regarding how IS fit into the institution. Following this, the findings of this study will be discussed. Finally, the implications of this study on the institution will be evaluated.

Purpose of Research

The purpose of this Action Research is to understand the struggles of IS in Japanese universities and promote programs geared at alleviating IS loneliness and social isolation. Knowledge generated from this research is expected to inform this higher education institute, and possibly other higher-education institutions, how to better accommodate their international student population.

Research Questions

Cycle 1 Questions

- 1.) What are the experiences and perceptions of IS at a private university in Japan?
- 2.) How do IS navigate the current system?
- 3.) How effectively do IS form social friendships and networks with DS?

Cycle 2 Questions

- 1.) What is the impact of an intentional IS support program on the belongingness experienced by IS students at a private university in Japan?
- 2.) How effectively do IS form social friendships and networks with DS?
- 3.) How can IS and DS social networks and friendships be improved?

Overarching Question

- 1.) How can interventions be developed and implemented to increase a sense of belongingness and positive feelings among IS at a private university in Japan?

Context Analysis

The context of this research is a private research science university in Tokyo, Japan. Originally existing as part of a larger prestigious Tokyo university, it gained independence over 140 years ago. This university is a well-regarded institute and has produced a Nobel Prize winner. The increase in international students over the years has been slow and still remains at 3% of the entire student population. Essentially, 97% of students are Japanese. These minority international students may be subject to oppression and “othering” (categorizing outside people as “them” rather than “us”). In this section, I will talk about the potential oppression IS face at this institution. This will hopefully provide context into the value of the research findings.

Identities and Positionality within The Institution

The positionality of international students living as a *gaijin* (lit. outside person), or foreigner, in Japan could be the subject of much research. For the purpose of this dissertation, I hope to give a brief overview of international student identity, positionality, and the cultural capital afforded to IS within this institution and Japanese society in general.

To better elucidate Japanese views of immigrants, it may be useful to unpack the term *gaijin*. Although *gaikokujin* (outside country person) and *gaijin* (outside person) share a similar linguistic construction, Curtis (2011) argues that the former is used primarily for official documents while the latter is in common usage in spoken Japanese. More recently, there has been a pushback against the term *gaijin* by *Ainu*, or indigenous Japanese people, and *burakumin*, or ethnic Korean Japanese (Curtis, 2011, p. 44). This suggests that some find the word offensive. For this reason, I will use the form *gaikokujin* from here on.

In my experience living in Japan for 17 years, there is a distinction to be made between visible *gaikokujin*, or non-Asian foreigners, and invisible, or Asian foreigners. Essentially, international people of Asian descent may blend in more than other non-Asian people. International students belonging to the

visible *gaikokujin* category are met with both privilege and exclusion, whereas the so-called “invisible *gaikokujin*” are potentially subject to more societal pressures to fit in. As Murphy-Shigematsu (2000) suggests, Japanese naturalizers have historically put pressure on Asian foreigners to change their names to further acclimate to Japanese society. This same pressure has not been applied to non-Asians. While this may seem like a privilege, it may highlight a perception that non-Asians cannot pass as Japanese, so there is no point in adopting Japanese names (Shigematsu, 2000, p. 208).

When considering international peoples’ cultural capital in Japan, it would be an oversight to not consider gender as a further oppression pressure point in a traditionally male-dominated society. According to the university website, 75% of students enrolled identify as male, while 25% identify as female. Female international students face oppression along multiple fronts. As Barrett (2004) illustrates, historically women in Japan have been confined to roles of *ryousai kenbo* or “good wife, wise mother.” While some legal steps have been made in favor of gender equality, these steps have perhaps not fully trickled down to the minds of employers (Barrett, 2004, p. 1).

As an international teacher, discussed in detail previously in the positionality section of this paper, I am also subject to oppression within Japan and this institution. This potentially affects my efficacy as a change agent. When discussing my problem of practice involving IS with colleagues, coworkers, and various stakeholders, there was a sentiment expressed akin to “Why should we (the institution) focus on a small population of students rather than the bulk of our students.” Fellow colleagues expressed a concern that focusing on IS would detract attention from domestic students. This sentiment itself may be evidence of the oppression international people face at this institution and in Japan. I did my best to dispel this idea by describing a win/win/win situation for all stakeholders (discussed in previous sections of this paper).

Findings

This section will discuss findings in the context of my institution and the extant literature. The three findings were 1.) IS experienced loneliness and feelings of not mattering/belonging, 2.) intervention empowered IS to make a change at the institution, and 3.) mixer events helped integrate IS, helping them feel that they belong and matter. Following a description of each finding, I will discuss the implications for the university.

Finding 1: International Students Experience Isolation, Loneliness, and Not Mattering/Belonging

Throughout Cycle 1 and Cycle 2, a theme continually emerged in the data. This theme, expressed by the majority of IS I interviewed at this Japanese university, was feelings of isolation in the form of loneliness, not mattering, and/or not belonging. Although my initial presupposition was that IS would benefit from the existence of English as a Medium of Instruction (EMI), this was not supported by the data emerging in Cycle 1. From institutional documents, I learned that most students were not from places we typically think of as English-speaking countries. In fact, only three of the 719 international students were from countries where English is the primary language (America, Canada, and Australia respectively). Additionally, EMI and EDP programs were already in existence in this institution. Many of the participants in Cycle 1 interviews reported already taking classes entirely in English.

In Cycle 1, it became clear that social isolation (loneliness, not belonging/mattering) was a bigger issue, and I would need to focus on this problem if I were to claim to be listening to the participants. In fact, 90% of the participants mentioned this issue even though I was not asking about it during the first six interviews. This social isolation was made clear in the following excerpts from IS interviews:

“Making friends and finding support systems inside the university and overall, like, like getting used to the Japanese life. For that one I need some help.” (Tay, Cycle 1 Interview, 2022)

“I think [the university staff] they do their best to, to, to provide me a lot of informations, like maybe I have to ask them more about like how, how to get friends.” (Hira, Cycle 1 Interview, 2022)

“[...] even the people who could speak really good Japanese they tell me that, oh they find it difficult to have, to make friends. They do have ‘friends’, in quotes, ‘friends’ that, for example, you have you do practicals together, you take classes together.” (Salim, Cycle 1 Interview, 2022)

Combatting isolation with social interaction, particularly with groups outside their own, may strengthen IS’s cultural and linguistic fluency through cross-cultural interaction (Bradford, 2013; Galloway et al., 2017; Phuong & Nguyen, 2019). Further, research indicates that increased interaction between IS and DS resulted in better IS grades and retention rates (Glass & Westmont, 2014). Glass and Westmont (2014) also suggest that “cultural events, leadership programs, and community service enhanced a sense of belongingness, buffered the effects of racism, and provided a secure base for the exploration of cross-cultural relationships” (p. 106).

Results in Cycle 1 led me to believe that IS needed a voice and platform on campus. A home away from home so to speak. At this point, I gained institutional approval to start the Cultural Awareness Circle. This group met on Mondays and gave students a forum to discuss international issues in a safe space while also strategizing ways to improve situations for IS.

Finding 2: Intervention Empowered International Students

The formation of the Cultural Awareness Circle functioned as a cultural center or hub for minority international students on campus. It gave them a voice and empowered them with change agency. Research suggests that similar cultural hubs and cultural centers have provided multiple benefits for minority students at other universities. These benefits include a dedication, on the part of the institution, to multiculturalism (Jenkins, 2008; Princes, 1994). This in turn makes the minority students feel as though they matter (Davenport, 2013; Toya, 2011) and have a sense of belongingness

(Welch, 2008). These groups also provide a safe space for marginalized groups (Boyd, 2016; Ludlow, 2004), giving them a so-called home-away-from-home (McDowell & Higbee, 2014).

During Cycle 1 and Cycle 2 interviews and questionnaires, it became clear that this social aspect of student life was important. During the Cycle 2 exit interview, the interviewed student even suggested they had sought psychological and medicinal intervention at the campus health center due to depression. This student reported being able to speak freely during the Cultural Awareness Circle meetings and mixer events. A Japanese teacher attending one of the mixer events reported to me his surprise that a student who was typically shy and quiet in his class was talking and taking a leadership role during the mixer event. Students attending these events reported feeling welcomed and accepted, interacting with others, and making friends. This empowerment of minority students supports the necessity for this type of intervention.

In addition to creating a safe space for IS to mingle, discuss international issues, and strategize change agency, it was also important to create the environment and conditions for IS to interact with other students, helping to combat feelings of isolation. Together with participating members of the Cultural Awareness Circle, we created two mixer events with the purpose of decreasing IS isolation, increasing transnational interaction, friendships, and networking, and creating a sense of belonging and mattering for minority students on campus. This empowerment of IS impacted the participants ability to find their voice and interact more openly. This is evidenced by the following excerpts from the exit interview conducted with an IS participant:

“Before the event I saw the university is just the place I took the lecture and I come, and I come back home. It's just this. Only one function and I don't have connections with others; pretty lonely. But after that event I, I know I can talk with others.” (Sira, Exit Interview, 2023)

Finding 3: Mixer Events Integrated International Students

Questionnaires given after the mixer events indicate that participants met people from other countries and made friends during the event. They also reported feeling welcomed and accepted. This suggests that events like these can help both international and domestic students who are experiencing social isolation on campus. In addition to the questionnaire data, increased interaction was also evidenced during the exit interview. Moreover, the participant seemed to have a more positive feeling about DS who attended the events. Please consider the following excerpts:

“I think it's different from the daily life. Um, the people I connect there is very different from the, the normal Japanese people. I think the Japanese people [at the event and circle meetings] are more open.”

(Sira, Exit Interview, 2023)

“I think people in the event are more friendly, easy-going” (Sira, Exit Interview, 2023)

As previously mentioned, combatting isolation with social interaction, particularly with groups outside their own, may strengthen IS's cultural and linguistic fluency through cross-cultural interaction (Bradford, 2013; Galloway et al., 2017; Phuong & Nguyen, 2019). Research also indicates that IS may benefit from increased social interaction by achieving better grades resulting in higher retention rates (Bowman et al., 2019; Bronkema & Bowman, 2019; Krieg et al., 2024; Rasco et al, 2023).

Conclusion

There were three main findings of this Action Research. The first finding, from Cycles 1 and 2 indicated that international students experienced difficulty making friends and social networks; particularly with domestic students. This finding is supported by research regarding IS solation and loneliness in America, Australia, and the UK (Arkoudis et al., 2019; Erichsen & Bolliger, 2011; Girmay & Singh, 2019; Khawaja & Stallman, 2011; Sawir et al., 2008; Trice, 2007; Wawera & McCamley, 2020).

The second finding was that the Cultural Awareness Circle empowered students by providing this minority group a hub and safe space to discuss and strategize positive change in the institution. This

may be in line with some of the positive impacts university cultural centers have provided minority groups in America. These positive impacts were the institutional display of dedication to multiculturalism (Jenkins, 2008; Davenport, 2013; Princes, 1994), the creation of a safe space for minority students (Boyd, 2016; Ludlow, 2004; McDowell & Higbee, 2014) and increasing self-esteem and graduation rates (Chiang, 2020; Stovall, 2000; Maramba & Palmer, 2014; Tinto, 1994, 1996). The Cultural Awareness Circle functioned as a cultural center for students to convene and discuss issues related to race, culture, gender, and international issues. It gave these students a platform to plan events of their own design based on research. This empowerment led to two mixer events.

The third finding was that mixer events helped integrate IS with people from other cultures. This is in line with research at other institutions (Ene, 2021; Li et al., 2018) that indicates mixer events have the potential to decrease student isolation and loneliness. Although the research regarding the positive impact of mixers is somewhat limited, respondents in our research indicated that they did meet people from different cultures and formed friendships. Respondents also indicated that the events gave them a more positive feeling of the university.

Implications for The Organization

In my first year of this doctoral program, I had biases that I was unaware of. I viewed social justice and action through a myopic lens of my own experiences. I subconsciously believed that the most appropriate change for students in my institution was the change that would incidentally benefit me the most. As an American expatriate in Japan and a native English speaker, I felt the university I worked at needed to better accommodate native English speakers. What I discovered was that there were English programs already in place and that the vast majority of IS were not native English speakers. I was surprised when I discovered that of the 719 IS, only three were from similar backgrounds as me. Only three IS were from countries where English was the primary language.

When I looked past my biases, I found that I was forced to listen to what the participants in the study were trying to convey about their experiences. Instead of searching for excerpts that confirmed my biases, I was left to scrap my preconceived notions and truly listen. When I did that, I heard something more profound in the students' voices. I discovered that they were experiencing isolation and loneliness in the world's most populous city and within a large university.

I believe that through the formation of a Cultural Awareness Circle and resulting mixer events, participants were able to interact with members of the academic community on their own terms. They were able to design the strategies for change, envisage events, and increase student interaction. I believe that when these students saw that they were not weak and voiceless, they didn't need me anymore. This transition happened faster than I thought it would. A few times I arrived at the Cultural Awareness Circle a few minutes late and students were already engaging in discussions and planning. At one of the mixer events, a Japanese teacher described being surprised by the leadership of a student who was usually shy and introverted in his class. I was surprised too as it was as if we knew two different students with the same appearance. I knew a student who initiated discussions and led the group. The Japanese professor knew a shy international woman who was outnumbered in the class by gender and nationality.

Cultural Awareness Circles and mixer events provide the institution with a more well-adjusted international student population. Being well-adjusted and better integrated into the academic community offers the university more productive and engaged students. Evidence from Cycle 1 suggested that IS were doing the bare minimum without exerting themselves academically. As one student said, "I just had to be there and then like submit uh a report or something, and I submitted in English and that's ah, no exams, or I don't need to listen to what they [lecturers] say." I believe we can inspire more from the global academics this university attracts. Japanese education, represented through this university, has a lot more to offer transnational students.

My hope, and recommendation, is that the university continues to allow these members to meet and discuss strategies for change. The cost of this intervention is only a room, some food, and beverages. This circle and the resulting events provided the opportunity for intercultural connections and friendships that may extend into the future. It gave both IS and DS a more positive feeling about the university. These students who, according to one participant, felt like “extra chairs” can start to fill those chairs and take an active role in the academic community they rightfully belong to.

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Appendix A: Research Design

Methodology

In this section, I will discuss qualitative research (qual) and how it fits into the philosophy and practice of Action Research (AR). I will first discuss my Problem of Practice (PoP) and give an overview of qual and AR practices. Next, I will examine how Qual and AR praxis relates to my PoP. Finally, I will discuss the methods by which participants were selected, interviews were conducted, codes were applied, and member checking was engaged. These steps helped me better assess emerging themes in the data.

Qualitative Research

The paradigm of social constructivism is an important justification for the use of qualitative research. Contrasting the objective and universally generalizable truths sought by quantitative research, Kukla (2000) suggests that the properties of reality are co-created by members of a group or society. Kim (2001) furthers this point by suggesting that for social constructivists, reality “does not exist prior to its social invention” (Kim, 2001, p. 3). Essentially, the notion of objective reality may be more elusive and entangled in subjectivity than previously thought.

Qualitative research offers researchers and practitioners an opportunity to glimpse reality as it is experienced on the individual level. Semi-structured interviews, observations, and focus groups are some of the qualitative methods at the disposal of qualitative researchers (Jamshed, 2014). These methods are attempts to better understand the nature of reality as it is reflected in the consciousness of individual observers.

Action Research Methodology

Action research is a methodology for applying change to a problematic system. When a system is faulty, some members are potentially marginalized or underrepresented. As Avison (1999) points out, action research applies change in a framework where participants mutually agree on the ethical

acceptability of interventions (p. 94). Social activists applying this approach do not work unilaterally, but rather in conjunction with stakeholders, organizational leaders, colleagues, and other community members. As Baum et al. (2006) clarifies, AR attempts to understand reality through a co-created change and reflection process. The participatory, democratic, and self-reflective nature of AR allows change agents many iterative cycles to remedy potential problems within a system.

Rationale for Action Research Methodology

My research examined the experiences and perspectives of a small minority group existing within a largely homogenous system. The IS minority group at this institution are perceived as outsiders, or fringe members of an otherwise exclusively Japanese academic institution. As Liddicoat (2007), citing Masden (1997), suggests, some Japanese hold a “we/they” perspective when describing Japanese vs. non-Japanese people. International students may feel othered in a society that holds strong views of national identity connected to the Yamato race (Liddicoat, 2007). As such, Action Research offered the opportunity to empower nonprivileged outsiders with strategies to gain more equitable access to Japanese academic resources. It offered the potential to give a voice to the voiceless, and thus better understand the experiential knowledge of these member participants.

Interviews and Coding

Ten interviews were conducted during Cycle 1 with IS members at this university, each lasting approximately 30 minutes in length. The interviews were recorded with the participants’ approval, but only their voices were captured for transcription purposes. Snowball sampling (Parker et al., 2019) was used in an unpremeditated manner. Parker et al. (2019) describe snowball sampling as involving a small initial sample of members (seeds) who recommend other agreeable participants. In the case of this research, the first member participant was outwardly enthusiastic and talked to their friends about participating.

Pseudonyms were used and some interview data was redacted to preserve the anonymity of participants, peers, and teaching staff. Open, axial, and selective (OAS) coding (Scott & Medaugh, 2017; Vollstedt & Rezat, 2019; Williams & Moser, 2019) was used to assess data and chart it along emerging themes. The themes were organized in a codebook and the themes most pertinent to the research questions were selected for discussion in this paper.

Participants were given an IRB-approved form with a contact number to Northeastern University. This provided participants with a method of voicing their concerns in an indirect and anonymous manner. The participants were also told they could contact me if they wanted to see the results of the research. I informed the participants of my intent to remain open and transparent in my data-collecting methodology. I also informed the participants that all data will be anonymized upon completion of the study, and that they could refuse to take part in the study at any time.

Data Collection and Analysis: Cycle 1

Participants

The main participants in my research were international students (IS) and domestic students (DS). These members were recruited through convenience and snowball sampling (Parker et al., 2019). These members frequented the International Lounge (IL) space and volunteered their time to help the ongoing research efforts. As the IL provided a good mix of international and domestic students who were interested in international matters, it seemed the ideal location for the participants to meet. Both domestic and international students participated in the action research with the goal of improving the international atmosphere of the university. IS participated in 11 interviews, ten during Cycle 1, and one exit interview during Cycle 2. Both DS and IS participated in strategizing better ways to integrate IS in this academic institution. Ultimately, both DS and IS planned and attended mixer events aimed at building transnational friendships and networks.

During Cycle 1, I employed semi-structured interviews and then evaluated the data using OAS coding (Scott & Medaugh, 2017; Vollstedt & Rezat, 2019; Williams & Moser, 2019). Ten interviews were conducted with IS for roughly 30 minutes. After the interviews were completed, the recordings were transcribed and coded using OAS (see figure 6). Essentially, the researcher went through the transcripts to identify salient moments within the dialogues. Excerpts were highlighted and then grouped in multiple categories. These categories were then examined to identify emerging threads and themes within the data. Finally, a report was written regarding the codes, categories, and themes for enhanced member checking (Candela, 2019) where participants are debriefed regarding the themes and codes to verify if they truly reflect the participants' experiences. Member checking took place both in person and through e-mail.

Figure 6

Process of coding and member-checking

Staff members of the Kyoto liberal arts department and administrators in Building 1 acted as essential allies in creating positive change at the institution. Accessing the IL, reserving the room for events, acquiring money for food and drinks, and having events officially advertised through the school website required these stakeholders' involvement. As such, they proved essential participants in the study, with two members frequently joining the events. One of the participating members was the department head. This member's involvement and support were of critical importance to the intervention's success. It was also important to keep these internal stakeholders in the loop as to the affairs of the Cultural Awareness Circle. This helped legitimize the Circle.

Data Collection and Analysis: Cycle 2

The Cycle 1 findings suggested IS may feel neglected or ignored, perhaps due to cultural and linguistic differences. The findings also suggested that IS are left to single-handedly navigate the Japanese university system, without a support system. I also conducted a baseline questionnaire with 111 IS respondents. Data from this questionnaire supported Cycle 1 data indicating IS isolation. For these reasons, in Cycle 2 I started a Cultural Awareness Circle comprised of DS and IS members. This group strategized ways to bridge the linguistic and cultural gap potentially hindering IS from acclimating to their new academic environment. This effort positively contributed to IS feelings of belonging within this institution. Being cognizant of Japanese culture, I structured my action step around the interpersonal concept of *nemawashi* (going around the root). *Nemawashi*, discussed in further detail below, assisted in instigating change without interrupting the Japanese sense of institutional harmony.

The goal of this research proposal was to increase IS assimilation and integration into the university community resulting in increased IS feelings of belonging. The data from Cycle 1 painted a picture of students feeling excluded and neglected. I believe that building a Cultural Awareness circle, or club, helped remedy some feelings of being stranded and alone.

Below, I will talk about action steps geared toward developing a Cultural Awareness Circle to act as a safe space and support system for neglected IS. This step empowered students to strategize ways to improve the institution's approach to IS. IS, alongside myself and DS, organized international and domestic student mixer events. These events contributed to better integration of IS within the university community.

Participants

The participants in the second cycle of research included both IS and DS enrolled at this university. Participants were both graduate and undergraduate students at my institution of employment. Participants communicated with me and others in English and/or Japanese based on

student linguistic limitations. Most students were able to speak English, but some students either could not speak English or perhaps preferred to speak Japanese. One student in Cycle 1 could not complete the interview in English and needed to speak Japanese.

Both convenience sampling (Etikan et al., 2016) as well as snowball sampling (Parker et al., 2019) were employed to gather participating members. In other words, the students who frequent the International Lounge space were approached about volunteering in the Cultural Awareness Circle, contributing to convenience sampling. These students often referred their friends, contributing to snowball sampling. Posters as well as word-of-mouth also contributed to the number of participating members. The only exclusionary criterion was that participants must be students at this university and speak either Japanese and/or English.

Procedures

There were basically five procedures engaged in during the Cycle 2 action steps. The first was *nemawashi* (discussed in greater detail above), which is a Japanese interpersonal procedure involving gaining consensus for ideas before bringing them up in meetings. It was important for me at this step to make sure that everyone was aware of my intervention intentions before blindsiding colleagues with initiative ideas during a meeting. Colleagues have a right to be “in the loop”, or privy to initiative ideas before being asked to comment on them during official meetings.

The second procedure was to gather baseline data before intervening. Essentially, I wanted to understand where IS were prior to our intervention efforts to better gauge whether we were having the desired effect. The baseline questionnaire was adapted from Hagerty & Patusky's (1995) Sense of Belonging Instrument (SOBI). The changes made to this questionnaire were removing some unrelated questions as I was told by university administrators that the questionnaire should not be more than 20 questions. I was able to whittle the questionnaire down to 23 questions. I also made some of the

questions more culturally specific to Japan. For example, I differentiated between making friends with other IS, and making friends with DS.

The third procedure was to start the Cultural Awareness Circle in September of 2023. This circle comprised of IS and DS, met weekly for the purpose of interacting, discussing cultural issues, and strategizing ways to better integrate international students into the university's academic community. Generally, 5-10 students joined our weekly meetings, with a good mix of both IS and DS members. This circle planned and hosted two international mixer events with the purpose of increasing IS and DS friendship formation and networking.

The fourth procedure was the hosting of two international mixer events in the International Lounge space in the main lecture hall on campus. One event, the World Snack Event, was held in November and included both IS and DS who brought snacks from their respective countries for the purpose of sharing something cultural and interacting with others from diverse cultural backgrounds. The second event, the World Holiday Event, was also well-attended by both IS and DS. This event incorporated less teacher talk time, instead favoring more student interaction time. Both events were two hours long, from 1:00 p.m. to 3:00 p.m.

The final procedure was an exit interview with an IS who seemed unsatisfied with the events' efficacy (based on questionnaire data gathered after each event). This student met with me for a 30-minute semi-structured interview with the purpose of better understanding this student's experiences with the Cultural Awareness Circle and mixer events. This interview helped the researcher understand the psychological issues isolation may cause IS, how the intervention addressed those issues, and how intervention could proceed in the future.

Data Analysis: Cycle 2

Data Analysis

During Cycle 1, I employed semi-structured interviews and then evaluated the data using open, axial, and selective coding (Corbin & Strauss, 1990). In cycle 2, I employed a baseline questionnaire and created a chart to analyze the mean scores of 111 respondents. I also employed 2 questionnaires at the culmination of two mixer events hosted by the Cultural Awareness Circle. Finally, I conducted a semi-structured interview with a participating IS at the culmination of the intervention.

This research incorporated Chase's (2017) "enhanced member checking" process. Candela (2019) describes member checking as a form of data triangulation where data is checked to ensure validity. Unlike traditional member checking as described by Lincoln & Guba (1986) as a final terminal step to cross-check data, Chase's (2017) suggests that enhanced member checking is a continual method for "co-creating a participant narrative" (p. 2688).

I anticipated some barriers and challenges in that IS are, by nature, a transient group. It is, for example, not uncommon for a student to be at this institution on a short student visa. For this reason, I had to conduct interviews quickly, and sometimes e-mails were exchanged in cases where IS were going to their home country shortly after.

Another challenge was linguistic barriers. I could not assume that all IS speak English or Japanese. I was able to conduct most interviews in English, but one interview had to be conducted in Japanese. I did not want student participants to view this project as an English-language endeavor. As an English teacher, some students may have felt pressure to interact with me in English, or that the activities and conversations in the Cultural Awareness Circle must be conducted in English. In the interest of not excluding members of the international or domestic community on campus, I made it clear that the circle is not necessarily solely focused on English. If, for example, participating members

are discussing cultural awareness issues in Japanese, I still considered this a success. For the sake of my personal involvement, I was limited to English and Japanese communication.

Ethical Considerations

Coghlan & Shani (2005) warn us of the multitude of unanticipated ethical issues that may arise during prolonged engagement with human subjects. Essentially, these issues may arise suddenly and in a manner that the researcher cannot predict. For this reason, it was important for me to keep my colleagues, peers, teachers, and doctoral chair involved in every step of the research process. If an ethical issue arose, strategies to move forward in the most appropriate manner could be decided by committee, rather than unilaterally.

With an Action Research study, it is necessary to interview students as participants. I continually strived to make participants feel unpressured to participate or produce specific results. Although I did not experience this during this research, there may be a situation where I am directly connected to the student's grade. I informed the students that their participation would not affect their class outcome in any manner. The American Psychological Association, in its standards for ethical AR practice, advises not only obtaining informed consent but also refraining from offering excessive financial incentives (Tomal, 2010). Participants were made aware that participation is entirely voluntary, without financial remuneration.

In accordance with the IRB, all participants were given a consent form with a contact number for Northeastern University. I asked the students if they understood the form and if they would like me to translate it. The Northeastern contact number provided participants with a method of voicing their concerns in an indirect and anonymous manner.

Additionally, I strived to present data in a manner in which participants cannot be identified. Winter (1987) suggests that it is the researcher's responsibility to ensure anonymity. To alleviate

confidentiality concerns, I inform students that all data will be anonymized upon completion of the study.

As Winters (1987) suggests that participants must have equal access to data generated during the study, I asked participants if they would like to be informed of the research results. I also provided them with my contact information if, at any time, they would like to know the results. Participants were also advised that they could use this contact information to opt out of the research at any time.

Trustworthiness

To help ensure trustworthiness in this research endeavor, I employed several of the techniques of Lincoln & Guba (1985). These techniques are geared toward enhancing credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. I will discuss the techniques I am employing in relation to these four points of trustworthiness.

Regarding credibility, this study employs prolonged engagement (Lincoln & Guba, 1985) in a near-natural setting (Li, 2004) in order to build trust, comfortability, and rapport with participants. The researcher met with student participants in the International Lounge in the central lecture building on campus over an extended period of time. As mentioned, prolonged engagement (Lincoln & Guba, 1985) is an important factor in establishing credibility. The weekly meetings continued for an entire semester to relieve initial uneasiness and “give the researcher as well as the respondents opportunities to test their own biases and perceptions” (Li, 2004, p. 304).

To help further ensure credibility, the researcher engaged in member checks (Lincoln & Guba, 1985) to ensure that the description of the qualia experienced by participants is accurate. This helped ensure that the researcher did not incorrectly represent the participants' views.

Finally, I have made efforts to collect more than one data source for the purposes of triangulation. To help establish credibility, data was collected at different times during the prolonged

research engagement (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). I also utilized the help of colleagues, doctoral teachers, my chair, and participants to assist in analyst triangulation (Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

Concerning transferability, I strived to include as much detail as possible to allow the reader to potentially apply elements of this research to their own environment if applicable. As Shenton (2004) explains, “To allow transferability, they [the researchers] provide sufficient detail of the context of the fieldwork for a reader to be able to decide whether the prevailing environment is similar to another situation” (p. 63).

Concerning dependability and confirmability, the researcher consulted various external auditors (Lincoln & Guba, 1985) in the form of doctoral professors, colleagues, classmates, and my doctoral chair. I also maintained thorough notes and documentation for the purposes of creating an audit trail, which can be reviewed at any time. Ang et al. (2016) advise that the researcher must “describe in detail how data were collected, how categories were derived, and how decisions were made throughout the research” (p. 1864). The e-Portfolio I developed alongside my doctoral chair is helping me store all my dissertation work for potential future audit.

Limitations

There are linguistic limitations to this research in that participants are relaying their experiences in their second (L2) or third language (L3). Of the ten participants interviewed in Cycle 1, none originated from an English-speaking country such as America or England. As a result, participants sometimes had difficulty finding the correct words to express themselves. To help counter this limitation I tried to be as patient as possible, and allow the interviewees the extra time to formulate their thoughts into their second (L2) or third language (L3). One participant required the use of Japanese. In that instance, the interviewer and interviewee communicated in their L2, Japanese. To help mitigate any communication issues, the research applied negotiation of meaning tactics such as comprehension and confirmation checks, and clarification requests (Long, 1983).

Additionally, as this doctoral program was a learning experience, I recognize that more post-intervention data could have added greater depth to the research. The exit interview, or post-intervention interview, produced data from a student who participated in both the Cultural Awareness Circle and the mixer events. Questionnaires produced data from participants who attended the mixer events. It would have been useful to interview more students in this post-intervention phase, particularly students who participated solely in the Cultural Awareness Circle. This would have helped the researcher understand whether participation in the Cultural Awareness Circle alone impacted IS, and to what extent.

Finally, my positionality as an international liberal arts teacher in a Japanese science university may lend itself to some degree of researcher bias. My belief is that, as a non-Japanese person, I am perceived as an outsider by Japanese members of this university. As a liberal arts teacher in a science university, I am concerned that language classes are deprioritized. These biases may impact my research study in ways I am not always aware.

Appendix B: Dissemination Plan

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Perspectives on EMI among English Teachers at a Japanese Science University

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ABSTRACT: *Through the design and implementation of a survey, this paper has sought to better understand perceptions among educators in Japan concerning the readiness and necessity of English-taught programs in Japanese higher education institutions. The researchers surveyed both domestic and international teachers at a private science university in Japan and found that educators believe some struggles exist for Japanese students in English-taught classes. These struggles, specifically regarding cultural differences in teaching and learning styles, might hinder Japanese students' acclimation to English-taught courses. The respondents also felt that English-taught programs were necessary and benefitted both international and domestic students.*

KEYWORDS: English as a medium of instruction, international students, japanese higher education, passive learning

INTRODUCTION

The motivation for this study stems from a concern regarding the enrolment numbers of international students (IS) at the Japanese science university where the participants surveyed (n=20) teach as members of the English group within the liberal arts department. Theoretically, the lack of IS could be the result of an absence of programs that adequately accommodate global English-speaking students, such as English as a medium of Instruction (EMI). The term EMI, as sourced from Deardon (2014) is described as content courses being taught in English rather than the national language of the country.

The Japanese government has supported several policy initiatives to promote internationalization such as the 300,000 International Students Plan, Go Global Japan, Top Global University Plan, and Global 30 (Ota, 2018; Rose & McKinley, 2018). According to

Appendix C: Critical Reflection

Cycle 0 Critical Reflection

Introduction

This critical reflection will briefly give an overview of the experience I had taking the first courses in the Northeastern EdD program. Specifically, I plan to outline some of the struggles and successes I encountered making an annotated bibliography and baseline 0 plan. The annotated bibliography and baseline 0 components served as essential components towards developing my understanding of existing literature and devising a working plan for the initial cycles of my action research. As such, I feel I should focus on these components in this reflection.

Difficulties and Solutions

At the start of this EdD course, I found it somewhat daunting to get a handle on the existing research in English as a Medium of Instruction and Internationalization of higher education. It was difficult to know where to start reading. At first, I had to read everything I encountered in a somewhat indiscriminate manner. With so much written on the topic, it was tough to scratch the surface, but I found that the more I read, the more I understood what I needed to read. I learned how to read an article and then data mine the references for additional articles. There is a lot of detective work involved in digging into a topic, but I found that I was able to follow a trail of research to uncover more information. Cribbin (2011) describes a process of backwards and forwards chaining which extrapolates articles from one seed paper resulting in a network of authors and research papers. The annotated bibliography assignment helped me to develop this chaining skill significantly.

The Cycle 0 plan assignment helped me to better envisage how my action research project would take shape. While my problem of practice (PoP) was very clear in my head, it was difficult to see a viable path forward. The assignment also helped me to consider how my plans for change could both positively and negatively affect the greater organizational system. I learned that a plan for change

cannot be one that is done in an ad hoc manner, but one that must take into consideration the many moving parts existing within a greater system. It is perhaps an error in human thinking to imagine this one particular problem as existing in a vacuum, and therefore easily remedied. Learning about Stringer's (2007) concept of "Look, Think, and Act" is, I believe, a useful concept in maintaining an action research plan that exists in the present tense and considers the impact of incremental change. Action research, in my view, needs to not only involve action, but also response. The interplay between acting and responding is perhaps what makes AR such a powerful tool.

Progress

In Cycle 0, my research was still in the very early stages of development, but I felt that I was able to get a better sense of the existing research surrounding my PoP. I also felt I was able to develop some groundwork and germinal strategies that informed the Cycle 1 stage of my research. At this early stage, I felt another important progression was the early establishment a network of student peers, colleagues, and potential stakeholders who helped with the multilateral effort required in action research. I felt good about the first kilometer completed in this action research marathon.

Cycle 1 Critical Reflection

Difficulties

Cycle 1 was all about learning to understand my own biases and trying to look past them in order to truly hear what the participants were saying. As an American expatriate in Japan, I assumed other international people had similar needs to me. An example of this was my focusing on installing an English as a Medium of Instruction program at this school simply because that is something that would help people in my situation. When I looked past my biases, I started to see that international students at this institution don't necessarily need the same things I do. During semi-structured interviews, I was encountering students with better Japanese skills than English. I was meeting students from non-English as a primary language countries such as China, Korea, Vietnam, etc. During Cycle 0, I was surprised to

learn that of the 719 international students, only three students were from countries that have English as a primary language.

Progress

Cycle 1 has forced me to look past my biases and listen to what the participants need rather than what I think they need. Cycle 1 participants revealed deep loneliness and social isolation that I needed to address. I remember, after interviewing one student, I asked the student “What are you doing today now that the interview is finished?” I assumed that a young student would have lots to do in the world’s biggest city. This student said something akin to “I am going home. That is all I ever do after being on campus. I go home and wait for the next class.” This was after a 30-minute interview where I asked this student about whether they needed English classes. It was clear that a greater social need was not being fulfilled for this student.

Cycle 2 Critical Reflection

While Cycle 1 was about learning to look past my researcher biases, Cycle 2 was about learning to work with people as a team. I had to learn not to control the direction of the research, but let the data inform the action. There was a desire, on my part perhaps, to steer the action steps in a manner that suited my preconceived ideas. The problem with steering the action steps is that student participants may not buy into the direction the intervention is going. Frequent member checking in the form of meeting with participants during weekly Cultural Awareness Circle meetings, e-mail and Line messenger correspondence helped my gauge whether the students felt connected to the research and intervention methods.

Additionally, I learned how important words can be when making questionnaire items. Some words are loaded with unintended meanings. I came across this problem when I made a questionnaire for my World Snack event. In this questionnaire, I used the term “at home” without considering how this term could mean something different to each participating member. Upon member checking, I learned

that one student had a particularly lonely home life, and they were able to speak and interact during the event. "At home" may also be a poor choice of words when considering that some people may be victims in their own homes. It is possible that some participants may equate "home" with domestic violence or other forms of abuse. I learned a lot about my choice of words when creating a questionnaire. The questionnaire for the second event was revised to remove "at home" and instead use "welcomed."

Additionally, I learned that I can get in my own way. During the first mixer event, I felt the need to make the event fun. As a result, I played games and talked a lot. This may have been fun for some of the students joining, but it also limited their interaction time. The goal of the event was not for them to have fun only, but rather to interact with other students from diverse cultural backgrounds. I was essentially contributing to the problem in the first mixer event. As a result, I made an effort to make the second event about the students. In the second event, all activities were highly unstructured. The only structure was in my forming groups that mixed IS and DS. Other than that, they were free to interact.

I think the second event was perhaps less "fun" and more awkward at the beginning, but it also resulted in more student interaction. Awkward silence can be productive if that silence is filled with conversation. I sensed that more connections were happening when I took myself out of the equation. This was perhaps addition by subtraction. Ultimately, at the end of the second event students asked for a game, so I relented, but still they benefitted from the first 1.5 hours being unstructured.

In retrospect, I might have added some games to the second event. Games where the students were in charge. Perhaps a game like "Find someone who..." where students interact and find students with particular attributes. This kind of game may have worked well as an ice-breaker.

Additionally, during the exit interview, I learned that these are real people with real issues. When a student tells me that they are seeking psychological help and taking medicine, it puts me in a compromised position. I cannot simply be a detached researcher in this moment, as there can be

dangerous repercussions for being entirely aloof. I felt I needed to offer some supportive words during this interview to let the student know that they were not alone. I felt I had to be a friend to this person in this moment, rather than a researcher.

Appendix D: Sense of Belongingness Instrument

Sense of Belonging Instrument - (SOBI; Adapted from Hagerty & Patusky, 1995)

Please choose 1-5. 1 suggests you strongly disagree with the statement. 5 suggests you strongly agree. 3 suggests you are undecided. Please do not write your name as this questionnaire is anonymous.

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)

1. I am an important part of [school name redacted]. (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)
2. I have many friends at [school name redacted]. (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)
3. I have many good Japanese friends at [school name redacted]. (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)
4. My friendships at [school name redacted] feel like family. (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)
5. [School name redacted] feels like home to me. (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)
6. [School name redacted] does a good job of making international students feel included and important. (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)
7. I feel accepted by everyone at [school name redacted]. (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)
8. I have deep friendships with many Japanese students in my classes. (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)
9. I feel that I am part of a group at my university. (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)
10. I fit in with other Japanese students at my university. (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)
11. Being international (non-Japanese) is difficult here. (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)
12. If I need help, there is always someone I can ask. (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)
13. People at my university are outgoing. (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)
14. [School name redacted] feels big. (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)
15. I am part of a loving and caring environment on campus. (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)
16. My campus always has a welcoming environment. (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)
17. My university brings me comfort. (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)
18. I enjoy learning at [school name redacted]. (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)
19. I am excited to be a student at [school name redacted]. (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)
20. I always enjoy being on campus. (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)
21. I definitely will finish my degree. (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)
22. Most of my friends are other international students. (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)
23. I wish I had more Japanese friends. (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)

Demographics

How many years have you attended college including your current year? _____

How would you describe your gender identity?

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary/third gender
- Transgender
- Prefer not to say

What is your racial background?

- American Indian or Alaska Native
- Asian Indian
- Black or African American
- Chamorro
- Chinese
- Filipino
- Hispanic
- Japanese
- Korean
- Mixed race
- Native Hawaiian
- Other Asian (Hmong, Laotian, Thai, Pakistani, Cambodian, etc.)
- Other Pacific Islander (Fijan, Tongan, etc.)
- Samoan
- Vietnamese
- White
- Other _____
- Prefer not to say

Appendix E: Sense of Belongingness Instrument Data

Sense of Belongingness Instrument Mean scores (n=111)

<i>Questionnaire Item</i>	<i>Mean Score</i>
<u>I am an important part of this university.</u>	<u>2.91</u>
<u>I have many friends at this university.</u>	<u>3.09</u>
<u>I have many good Japanese friends at this university.</u>	<u>2.81</u>
<u>My friendships at this university feel like family.</u>	<u>2.87</u>
<u>This university feels like home to me.</u>	<u>2.88</u>
<u>This university does a good job of making international students feel included.</u>	<u>3.36</u>
<u>I feel accepted by everyone at this university.</u>	<u>3.41</u>
<u>I have deep friendships with many Japanese students in my classes.</u>	<u>2.74</u>
<u>I feel I am part of a group at my university.</u>	<u>3.43</u>
<u>I fit in with other Japanese students at this university.</u>	<u>3.29</u>
<u>Being international (non-Japanese) is difficult here.</u>	<u>2.81</u>
<u>If I need help, there is always someone I can ask.</u>	<u>3.64</u>
<u>People at this university seem outgoing.</u>	<u>3.12</u>
<u>This university feels big.</u>	<u>3.32</u>
<u>I am part of a loving caring environment on campus.</u>	<u>3.16</u>
<u>My campus always has a welcome environment.</u>	<u>3.33</u>
<u>My university brings me comfort.</u>	<u>3.3</u>
<u>I enjoy learning at this university.</u>	<u>3.54</u>
<u>I am excited to be a student at this university.</u>	<u>3.43</u>
<u>I always enjoy being on campus.</u>	<u>3.18</u>
<u>I definitely will finish my degree.</u>	<u>4.34</u>
<u>Most of my friends are other international students.</u>	<u>3.22</u>
<u>I wish I had more Japanese friends</u>	<u>3.6</u>

Appendix F: World Snack Event Questionnaire

World Snack Event: Questionnaire

* Indicates required question

1. Email *

2. What country are you from? *

出身国はどこ？

3. I met people from different countries today. *

イベントで異なる国の人と会うことができた。

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly Agree (とてもそう思う)

4. I will talk to people I met at the event again. *

イベントで会った人とまた話すことがあると思う。

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly (強くそう思う)

5. This event was inclusive to my culture. *

イベントは自分の文化に対してインクルーシブだった。

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (とてもそう思う) Strongly Agree (とてもそう思う)

6. I made friends at this event. *

イベントで友達を作ることができた。

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (とてもそう思う) Strongly Agree (とてもそう思う)

7. I will come to future events like this. *

またこのようなイベントに参加したい。

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (とてもそう思う) Strongly Agree (とてもそう思う)

8. I felt at home and accepted at this event.

イベントは居心地が良く、自分が受け入れられていると思えるものであった。

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (とてもそう思う) Strongly Agree (とてもそう思う)

9. Mixer events (Japanese and international students) are important.

日本人と留学生が交流できるイベントは重要である。

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (とてもそう思う) Strongly Agree (とてもそう思う)

10. I felt welcomed at this event.

イベントに歓迎されていると感じた。

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (とてもそう思う) Strongly Agree (とてもそう思う)

11. Events like this give me a more positive feeling about this school.

このようなイベントは大学に対してより肯定的な態度を持たせてくれる。

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree (とてもそう思う) Strongly Agree (とてもそう思う)

12. What would you change about this event (if anything)?

変えたとするとどのような変更をイベントに加えたいか。

Appendix G: World Snack Event Questionnaire Data

What country are you from?

8 responses

I met people from different countries today.

8 responses

I will talk to people I met at the event again.

8 responses

This event was inclusive to my culture.

8 responses

I made friends at this event.

8 responses

I will come to future events like this.

8 responses

I felt at home and accepted at this event.

8 responses

Mixer events (Japanese and international students) are important.

8 responses

I felt welcomed at this event.

8 responses

Events like this give me a more positive feeling about this school.

8 responses

What would you change about this event (if anything)?

3 responses

飲み物がもう少しあると嬉しい👍

ミュージックかける

何日か開催する

Appendix H: World Holiday Event Questionnaire Data

What country are you from? 出身国はどこ？

7 responses

I met people from different countries today. イベントで異なる国の人々と会うことができた。

7 responses

I will talk to people I met at the event again. イベントで会った人とまた話すことがあると思う。

7 responses

This event was inclusive to my culture. イベントは自分の文化に対してインクルーシブだった。

7 responses

I made friends at this event. イベントで友達を作ることができた。

7 responses

I will come to future events like this. またこのようなイベントに参加したい。

7 responses

I felt welcomed and accepted at this event.

イベントは居心地が良く、自分が受け入れられていると思えた。

7 responses

Mixer events (Japanese and international students) are important.

日本人と留学生が交流できるイベントは重要である。

7 responses

I felt welcomed at this event. イベントに歓迎されていると感じた。

7 responses

Events like this give me a more positive feeling about this school.

このようなイベントは大学に対してより肯定的な態度を持たせてくれる。

7 responses

Appendix I: Cultural Awareness Circle Fieldnotes

Meeting 1 (September 25, 2023)

This was the first meeting of the circle. I had e-mailed all the international students (IS) informing them that I would be at the International Lounge in the Lecture Hall building on Monday, September 25. I had also put up several fliers around campus months in advance. In fact, you can see one such flier attached to the whiteboard in the background. 8 students attended this meeting. One student was a participant I had interviewed in Cycle 1. This student had brought 2 friends, one Japanese, and the other Chinese. Other students attended based on, I presume the flier.

We had a great discussion during this meeting. I talked about the problem of practice involving international students having difficulty making friends and networks at this school. The students seemed very sympathetic to this problem. We discussed what the school was currently doing to remedy this problem, including mixer events. Most of the students seemed to suggest that these events were not successful. We also discussed some possible events we could host.

The student who brought his friends was very outgoing... perhaps a natural leader. I was pleasantly surprised at how he led the discussions and even suggested a whiteboard game we could play

at the end. I had not planned a game, but I think I will moving forward. A short game at the end adds some levity to the group and perhaps encourages them to keep coming. I also will encourage the students with leadership characteristics to continue leading the group. At the end of the meeting, I asked if people would be amenable to me contacting them via e-mail. They agreed, and I asked them to generate an e-mail list.

Meeting 2 (October 2, 2023)

I e-mailed the students from last week to remind them that we were meeting again this Monday. There were fewer students this time (n=5) but the discussion went much deeper. We discussed cultural differences between the East and the West, particularly related to teaching and learning styles. The Japanese agreed when I said that Japanese classes tend to be more teacher-oriented, resulting in a passive learning style. They also agreed that it is difficult to disagree with peers or superiors due to Japanese culture and the tendency to avoid confrontation. One international student said that English classes in Japan were too easy. He suggested that the textbooks and class contents were the type of thing Italians study in jr. high school.

We discussed IS isolation issues at length and possible events we could arrange. One international student suggested an international snacks event. In Asia, snacks are very ornately packaged and contain interesting flavors such as green tea mixed with chocolate. We agreed that an international snack event would be great idea.

Meeting 3 (October 9, 2023)

Today was National Sports Day in Japan, so many of the labs were shut down. Additionally, many classes were not being held. As a result of the national holiday and heavy rain, there were only 3 students at Cultural Awareness Circle. Fortunately, there was a new Japanese student who said she was drawn to the Circle from the flier. This new student was very enthusiastic about joining the circle each week and participated in a mixer event. I told her about the world snacks idea that an international

student had come up with. I added her name to the mailing list in order to remind her of the meetings each week.

This student told me that she had never had an international friend. She met an international student from Australia in high school, but the student was only in Japan for 2 weeks. She struggled to remember her name. I asked her why she felt some Japanese and international students were struggling to make friendships, and she said it was perhaps the result of a language barrier.

Meeting 4 (October 17, 2023)

I was not able to meet with circle members during the usual Monday timeslot. Instead, I e-mailed all circle members, and a few agreed to meet on Tuesday at 2:40. The female student from last week showed up and seemed very intent on helping with the International Snacks event. I felt like our meetings and strategies were too abstract and not moving quickly enough, so I decided to use a whiteboard to help keep us on track. This helped with event planning.

The whiteboard really helped move abstract ideas to more concrete plans. We agreed on a tentative date for the event, November 29th from 1:00 – 3:00 o'clock. During the Cultural Awareness Circle meeting, I asked if students checked their e-mail. I noticed many seemed surprised to find I had mailed them. I was told that international students prefer to use Line Messenger. One student invited me to the group, so I downloaded Line and accepted her invitation. I decided to send the group a Line message to invite them to the Cultural Awareness Circle, and also to tell them about the tentative plans to host an event.

Meeting 5 (October 23, 2023)

We returned to meeting on Monday at 2:40. Some new students joined after seeing my Line message. I used the whiteboard again to strategize the event. This time, I gave the students a goal of designing a poster for the event. Together, with the student participants, we used the whiteboard to plan an event poster, focusing on what information should be included and how we should describe the

event see. The student participants made some very good observations about potential pitfalls. One such pitfall was that some students may feel they have to attend the entire event (from 1-3 p.m.). This may exclude students who have classes from 2:40. We decided that we need to include a blurb on the poster that students can attend for the entire event or part of the event.:

Meeting 6 (October 30, 2023)

As this week fell on the mid-term exams, not many students showed up. I asked the students how we could promote the World Snack Event. The students mentioned that there is an International Affairs Office at the main campus that promotes events. I decided to call this office and begin advertisement procedures.

Meeting 7 (November 13, 2023)

Today, we talked about the event and one student mentioned that the school had not advertised the event yet on the website. I went back through my e-mails and realized that this was my fault. The office had written me asking to confirm the advertisement wording. I e-mailed them back and said the advert looked good and they told me the advertisement would be published today at 8 pm.

Meeting 8 (November 20, 2023)

Today, we discussed what items Japanese students could bring. There was a concern, among Japanese students, that their contributions would not be culturally interesting. As a result, we talked about perhaps bringing either 1.) A snack from their distinctive prefecture to share, or 2.) an international food as a show of solidarity with another country. We talked about how most international students were from China and Korea, and that these students may feel good to know that a Japanese student enjoys their country's food. We also talked about what shops and online stores sell Chinese and Korean items. I felt there was some buzz forming around the event.

Meeting 9 (November 27)

Today, group members noticed there was a Chinese student hovering around the door and peeking in for several minutes. We decided to go out to the hallway and greet this student. This student said he was looking in but too nervous to enter the room. He said he wanted to attend the event and bring a Japanese snack... he really likes Japanese snacks and wants to talk about his favorite Japanese foods. Of course, we told him that was perfectly acceptable. He left soon after as his class was starting soon.

Meeting 10 (December 18)

Today there were not many students in the lounge, but a student ally was there. I should mention, as I have not mentioned it before in these notes, that I have been lucky to have a student ally who has been helping me immensely with the IT aspects of my research. This student has been helping me create questionnaires and assisting me with translations.

Appendix H: Mixer Events Fieldnotes

World Snack Event (November 29th)

The event started at 1:00 and was slated to finish at 3 p.m. For most of the event, there were 13 students in attendance. From my count, there were 4 Japanese students, and 9 international students (all from China and Korea). One receptionist from the first floor came to the room before the event started because she wanted to contribute some Japanese snacks. She brought an entire bag of little Japanese snacks. This is one aspect of Japanese culture that is remarkable. People in Japan often want to help and contribute. The event mostly followed the plan.

In addition to 13 students, there were 4 teachers (including myself) who wished to join the event. One international teacher also volunteered to lead a Pictionary game at the end. At first, I put the students into groups based on numbers (focusing on mixing international students with domestic). I changed the groups many times so that everyone had a chance to meet and mingle. The conversation was almost entirely in English, but some students were speaking in Japanese. The conversation was so smooth in the groups that it was difficult to find a place to stop and change groups. It was also difficult to stop the conversation to introduce the snacks or the trivia game.

At the end of the event, many students approached me and asked for more mixer events. I felt there was a general positive response to the event. One of the teachers at the event told me that one of the international females in attendance was in his class last semester. He said the class was all boys except for this one international student. The teacher mentioned that, perhaps due to her gender and international status, she never spoke in that class. He was surprised she was talking so much at the event. I was surprised too as this student was taking charge of the event and leading discussions. She seemed very outgoing.

At the end of the event, and as students were leaving, I asked them to scan the QR code on their

phones in order to take the questionnaire. Additionally, posters with the QR code were posted on all the doors and tables of the Lounge area. The results of these questionnaires are discussed later in this paper. In addition, follow-up e-mails and member checking were conducted during the days following the event.

Second Mixer Event 12/20/2023

After the first event, some of the students requested a second event. As the group leader was at this event, I was able to initiate nemawashi during the event itself. We discussed having a holiday event on December 20th. My colleagues kept referring to this event idea as a “Christmas event”, but I wanted this to be a culturally diverse event, not an event that focuses on Christmas, English, or Western culture specifically. Despite my efforts, I could not steer my colleagues away from the December and Christmas connection. Even when I requested the event be dubbed “Holiday Event”, it was still referred to as a

“Christmas Event” in correspondences and advertisements. I was worried the religious connotations of “Christmas” might deter some students from joining.

Since nemawashi had already begun, I continued discussing the idea with several colleagues. The group and department leader suggested that I do not need to discuss it in a meeting as they felt I should begin preparations immediately. In lieu of a meeting, the initial nemawashi started an e-mail chain for institutional approval to use the international lounge space. I tried to make clear in my e-mail responses that I wanted to change this event from a teacher-centered focus to a student-centered focus in order to encourage networking and friendship building. On December 20th, we held the second mixer event. There were 12 students in attendance. The goal of this event was to have more discussion for the sake of IS and DS integration. We engaged in mixing and discussion for the first hour, but then students wanted to play Pictionary again like the first event. I obliged as I was outnumbered. After the event and as students left, I gave students the QR code for the survey.

Thank you for reading my dissertation. Never let anyone make you feel that you do not have value